

Altitude Physiology Expeditions (APEX) 7 Expedition Report

June - July 2025

Bolivia

Editors:

Mr David Geddes, Expedition Leader, APEX 7
Mr Cameron Norton, Expedition Leader, APEX 7

Authors:

Mr David Geddes, Expedition Leader, APEX 7
Mr Cameron Norton, Expedition Leader, APEX 7
Ms Anya Tan, Head of Research, APEX 7
Mr Ben Harrison, Head of Funding, Grants & Sponsorship, APEX 7
Ms Camille Maestelle, Head of Funding, Grants & Sponsorship, APEX 7
Ms Ella Andrea, Head of Volunteers, Wellbeing & Publicity, APEX 7
Ms Ella McElnea, Head of Volunteers, Wellbeing & Publicity, APEX 7
Ms Colette Revadillo, Head of Communications, APEX 7

Correspondence:

Mr David Geddes/Mr Cameron Norton, Expedition Leader
apex7@altitude.org/david.geddes@altitude.org

doi: 10.5281/zenodo.18792325

Version 1.1

April 2026

Website: www.altitude.org

Instagram: @AltitudeAPEX

Email: apex7@altitude.org

THE UNIVERSITY of EDINBURGH

University of BRISTOL

UNIVERSITY OF CAMBRIDGE

Nottingham Trent University

THE UNIVERSITY of EDINBURGH
Student Experience Grants

APEX 7 would like to thank the following organisations for their sponsorship, support, and grants, without any of whom the expedition would not be possible. Explore more of what our sponsors have to offer later in the report!

Contents

Foreword & Executive Summary

1. Introduction

- 1.1 APEX Expeditions & The APEX Charity
- 1.2 The APEX 7 Expedition: Aims
- 1.3 Expedition Synopsis
- 1.4 Report Scope & Structure

2. Expedition Contingent

- 2.1 Expedition Committee
- 2.2 Expedition Doctors
- 2.3 Expedition Volunteers
- 2.4 Partner Organisations & Supporters

3. Pre-Expedition Planning & Preparation

- 3.1 Planning Timeline
- 3.2 Committee Formation
- 3.3 Country & Site Selection
- 3.4 Institutional Approval & Risk Management
- 3.5 Logistical Operations
- 3.6 Medical Team Selection
- 3.7 Expedition Sustainability

4. The Research

- 4.1 Research Timeline
- 4.2 Research Projects
- 4.3 Research Reflections

5. Volunteer Experience

- 5.1 Volunteer Recruitment & Selection
- 5.2 Volunteer Demographics
- 5.3 Pre-Expedition Teambuilding
- 5.4 The Volunteer Experience
- 5.5 Volunteer Testimonies

6. Financial Report

- 6.1 Funding Strategy & Timeline
- 6.2 Income & Expenditure
- 6.3 Grant & Funding Landscape
- 6.4 Use of Surplus & Future Finances

7. Expedition Execution

- 7.1 Expedition Itinerary
- 7.2 Expedition Operations

8. Reflections & Next Steps

- 8.1 Key Achievements
- 8.2 Challenges & Lessons Learnt
- 8.3 Next Steps
- 8.4 Recommendations

9. Conclusion

Closing Pages

Foreword by Expedition Leaders

It is with immense pride that we present the APEX 7 expedition report, the culmination of over three years (and counting!) of tireless work by the APEX 7 team.

Sitting here reflecting on APEX 7's successes feels surreal. Neither of us expected, over four years after APEX 6, that we would be celebrating what has arguably been the most successful APEX expedition to date! What started as a drive for adventure quickly became something far bigger than we could have ever imagined. Organising an expedition on this scale – from managing intercontinental logistics, to securing funding and regulatory approvals – presented us with the most rewarding challenge of our university years.

The success of the APEX 7 expedition is a testament to the character and commitment of the people involved. We are immensely grateful to our organising committee, who balanced their demanding studies with thousands of hours of voluntary work to bring APEX 7 to life. We are truly honoured to have shared this experience with our 85 wonderful volunteers and 4 expedition doctors. To all of you: we hope you've gained as much from coming on APEX 7 as we have from leading it. It has been inspiring to watch lifelong friends form and to see such a strong sense of community built in the mountains.

We are also immensely proud of the ambitious research we conducted whilst on the expedition. The scientific spirit employed on APEX 7 has been wonderful to be part of, and we are very thankful to our academic supervisors and everyone behind the scenes who helped make this research a reality. Just as importantly, APEX 7 provided us with a unique platform to gain real, hands-on experience in medical research, fulfilling one of APEX's core missions.

Finally, as we reflect on the successes of the APEX 7 expedition, we also hold in our thoughts John Aravinth, a bright and enthusiastic volunteer who we tragically lost before he could join us in Bolivia. John's heart and passion for adventure embodied the very spirit of APEX. His memory was a constant source of inspiration throughout our journey, and it is with great respect that we have chosen to dedicate this expedition report to John and his family.

David Geddes & Cameron Norton

David Geddes Cameron Norton

**APEX 7 Expedition Leaders
April 2026**

Executive Summary

Background & Objectives

APEX 7 was a student-led, high-altitude clinical research expedition conducted between June 28th and July 13th 2025, in the Bolivian Cordillera Real mountain range. APEX 7 successfully took 97 expedition members (85 student volunteers, 4 expedition doctors, and 8 organising committee) from the University of Edinburgh to an elevation of 4,800 metres to conduct cutting-edge medical research.

APEX 7 was the seventh expedition in a series of expeditions designed, implemented and executed entirely by a committee of undergraduate medical students. The primary objectives were to investigate the effects of hypobaric hypoxia (low oxygen levels) on human physiology through seven distinct, ethically approved research studies. These projects sought to investigate the hormonal, genetic, metabolic, cardiovascular, dermatological, immunological and neurological responses to hypoxia.

Results

APEX successfully carried out each of the approved research studies, collecting tens of thousands of high-resolution data points. This dataset represents a significant contribution to our global understanding of hypoxic physiology. Furthermore, by taking 97 participants to 4,800 metres simultaneously, APEX 7 broke the record for the highest simultaneous controlled ascent in history.

Impact

The APEX 7 expedition delivered significant institutional and social impact beyond its scientific outputs:

- Inspiring future generations of clinical academics – APEX provided 85 student volunteers with intensive, hands-on experience with research methodology and execution in a unique field environment.
- Breaking financial barriers to participation – APEX 7 funded eight places for volunteers from widening-access backgrounds, ensuring that financial status was not a barrier to participation in clinical academia.
- Strengthening diplomatic relations – APEX 7 strengthened international academic ties through formal collaboration with Bolivian Scientists and strengthened British-Bolivian relations through the British Embassy.

Conclusion

All biological samples are currently undergoing laboratory analysis in the UK, and research manuscripts are in the drafting stages for submission to high-impact clinical journals. The following report highlights the operational logistics and frameworks required to execute the APEX 7 expedition, providing a strategic blueprint for future student-led research expeditions.

1. Introduction

1.1 APEX Expeditions & Charity

Founded in 2001 by medical students at the University of Edinburgh, Altitude Physiology Expeditions (APEX) is a student-led group that conducts research expeditions to high-altitude. APEX expeditions aim to explore and investigate how human physiology is impacted by high-altitude induced hypoxia (low oxygen).

Since its inception, APEX has undertaken seven major research expeditions. A defining feature of APEX is its organisation structure: each expedition, from conception to execution, is managed by a committee of undergraduate students under the supervision of senior clinical academics and established researchers.

Each APEX expedition is supported by the APEX charity (SC030345). The APEX charity serves to offer operational continuity between each expedition and is composed of previous expedition organisers, all of whom have gone on to impressive feats in their respective fields. The charity supports future expeditions by offering their experiences and mentorship to current organisers.

Beyond its primary research goals, APEX has a core educational aim: to provide undergraduate students with substantive, early-career experience in research methodology, logistical planning, and leadership. APEX therefore serves as a platform to empower the next generation of clinician-scientists, equipping them with the practical skills necessary for a future in academic medicine and medical innovation.

1.2 The APEX 7 Expedition: Aims

The most recent expedition, APEX 7, took place in June and July 2025, and comprised of the single largest simultaneous expedition conducted in APEX history. The expedition had the following high-level aims & objectives:

Research

To conduct high-quality research investigating human physiological responses to hypobaric hypoxia.

Operational

To conduct a safe and logistically successful high-altitude research expedition to the Bolivian Andes.

Educational

To provide unique educational and developmental experiences for volunteers, and to train and inspire future generations of academic clinicians.

1.3 APEX 7 Expedition Synopsis

The APEX 7 expedition took place in the Cordillera Real region of Bolivia between June 28th 2025 and July 13th 2025, an in-country duration of 16 days. The expedition consisted of a team of 97 members - including the organising committee, expedition doctors, and volunteers from the University of Edinburgh. The expedition went to La Paz, Bolivia (3600m) and Refugio Vista Panorámica, Huayna Potosí (4800m). The expedition was split into 3 distinct phases: an initial acclimatisation period in La Paz, followed by an ascent to Refugio Vista Panorámica for the majority of research, concluding with a descent and final stay in the capital, La Paz (Figure 1). A further detailed chronological account of the expedition is presented in section 7.

Figure shows overview of APEX 7 ascent profile and timeframes

1.4 Report Scope & Structure

This report provides a comprehensive account of the logistical, financial, and scientific aspects of the APEX 7 expedition, detailing its methodology, key findings, and reflections for the future. The initial sections outline the expedition contingent (Section 2), followed by a review of the pre-expedition planning process (Section 3). The report then explores and discusses: expedition research (Section 4), volunteer cohort (Section 5), and expedition finances (Section 6). Section 7 describes the expedition's in-country operations. The report concludes with a discussion of key achievements and reflections for the future (Section 8).

2. Expedition Contingent

2.1 APEX 7 Committee

The APEX 7 organising committee was made up of 8 senior medical students from the University of Edinburgh.

Cameron Norton
Expedition Leader

David Geddes
Expedition Leader

Anya Tan
Head of Research

Ella Andrea
*Head of
Volunteers &
Wellbeing*

Ella McElnea
*Head of
Volunteers &
Wellbeing*

Ben Harrison
*Head of Funding,
Grants &
Sponsorship*

Cami Maezelle
*Head of Funding,
Grants &
Sponsorship*

Colette Revadillo
*Head of
Communications*

2.2 APEX 7 Expedition Doctors

The 4 APEX 7 Expedition Doctors were selected after a rigorous selection process, and included specialists in general practice, anaesthetics, emergency medicine, and expedition medicine. See more about them and what they said about being part of the APEX 7 expedition here:

Dr Helen Gertig (Lead Doctor)

I'm a GP working in the Highlands of Scotland. I've been lucky to support expeditions all over the world, but APEX7 really stands out. It was inspiring, humbling, and quite frankly often hilarious to be able to support such a fabulous bunch of folk to reach the beautiful APEX7 mountainous research base, and a privilege to facilitate some top quality high altitude research.

The heady combination of altitude and research created some interesting medical scenarios that challenged us as a medical team but led to some participation-focused solutions allowing as many people as possible to reach their goals. It was fabulous to see such a successful, and more importantly, fun, expedition unfold - thank you to all of the APEX7 family for being so up for it!

Dr Francis Screech

I am an anaesthetics CT3 based in the southwest of England with an interest in providing medical care in remote and austere places. I also enjoy critical care and pre-hospital medicine. I have had the opportunity to work on a variety of expeditions across the globe, but APEX 7 was my first experience supporting a major research expedition, and what an incredible experience it was!

The trip was exciting, hilarious, humbling and inspiring. It challenged my decision making, treatment planning, and provided numerous logistical conundrums. I was so impressed by the professionalism and dedication of volunteers and committee members in ensuring the high quality research output of this trip. It was an immense privilege to have spent those wonderful weeks in our high altitude base camp with such an inspiring group!

Dr Nathan Hudson-Peacock

I'm a doctor based in London, working in emergency medicine and anaesthetics. I feel hugely privileged to have been a part of the medical team supporting APEX 7. The altitude brought all of its usual challenges with the full spectrum of altitude illnesses, and the research focus added its own complexities to our clinical decision making. We were certainly kept busy with blood sampling too, and it was great to be able to put our ultrasound skills to good use for the research projects requiring arterial blood samples!

Beyond the medical side of things, the expedition was just so much fun! Spending several weeks at high altitude with almost 90 students and a rather scary toilet-to-student ratio, the experience could have gone either way! Thankfully, the organisation of the leadership team was nothing short of incredible, and the resilience and determination of every single participant was inspiring to say the least. I felt truly welcomed from the very beginning, and I'm hugely grateful to have been a part of this expedition with plenty of hilarious memories and friends for life made along the way!

Dr Katie Ward

I am a GPST1 trainee based in North Yorkshire, with most of my prior clinical experience in intensive care and emergency medicine and a strong interest in expedition and wilderness medicine. I was one of four doctors supporting the APEX 7 expedition, providing medical support to almost 90 students!

Practising medicine at altitude brings a unique mix of unpredictability and problem-solving. During APEX 7, the demands of high-altitude research and expedition life meant the medical team had to stay adaptable, finding creative and pragmatic ways to keep people both safe and engaged with their projects. Watching such a motivated group of students support one another and thrive in a uniquely challenging environment made the expedition incredibly rewarding to be part of, and I feel very grateful to have shared the experience.

2.3 APEX 7 Expedition Volunteers

The APEX 7 volunteer contingent was made up of 85 students from the University of Edinburgh.

2.4 Partner Organisations & Supporters

APEX 7 was very lucky to have been supported by many companies, without any of whom the expedition would not have been possible. Here are some of our top partner organisations and supporters. More about other supporters can be found at the end of the report.

Bolivian Mountains were the primary in-country logistics partner of APEX 7 and were responsible for all logistical operations, including transport, facilities, and supplies.

Check them out here! www.bolivianmountains.com

Tiso was one of the APEX 7 kit sponsors, who were very kind to offer us the team jackets at a very brilliant price.

Check them out here! www.tiso.com

Workwear Express were one of the APEX 7 kit sponsors, who very kindly supported us with the expedition fleeces.

Check them out here! www.workwearexpress.com

The Medic One charity at RIE was the main supplier of our medical equipment, which was essential for expedition safety.

And finally, the APEX charity! Founded 25 years ago, the APEX charity has been essential in continuing the legacy of these expeditions and providing invaluable support and mentorship to current and future expedition organisers.

3. Expedition Planning & Preparation

3.1 Planning Timeline

Figure shows broad timeline for APEX 7 expedition planning and execution

3.2 Committee Formation

Formation of the APEX 7 organising committee started in December 2022. During this period, interest was gauged from prospective committee. Initial discussions within this group led to the decision of formal committee roles. A committee of 8 was decided: two expedition leaders, one head of research, two heads of funding, grants, and sponsorship, two co-heads of volunteers, wellbeing and publicity, and one head of communications. It was decided that the expedition leaders should be in different academic years to better distribute workload during varying periods of university commitments.

Election of the full APEX 7 committee took place at an annual general meeting held on 24th April 2023. During this meeting, the following roles were elected:

- Expedition Leader = Cameron Norton & David Geddes
- Head of Research = Anya Tan
- Head of Funding, Grants & Sponsorship = Ben Harrison & Camille Maezelle
- Head of Volunteers and Wellbeing = Ella Andrea, Ella McElnea
- Head of Communications = Colette Revadillo

Following the AGM, dedicated communication channels, including group chats and slack workspaces, were established for the new committee. Subsequently, between April and June 2023, each elected committee member took part in a handover process with their respective counterpart from the APEX 6 organising committee. This involved both verbal handovers and transfer of key documentation to ensure operational continuity. In June 2023, an APEX 7 google drive was created, providing the committee with a dedicated workspace and email address.

3.3 Country & Site Selection

Country & site selection for the APEX 7 expedition took place during the summer of 2023. Initial research explored potential host countries, with Ecuador and Bolivia emerging as the primary candidates for the expedition. Both Ecuador and Bolivia were deemed favourable countries due to their suitable high-altitude profiles and accessibility via international air routes. Both countries underwent a preliminary feasibility assessment during this time.

Ecuador

Ecuador was initially favoured as the primary country for the APEX 7 expedition, driven by the possibility of a novel APEX location, and the extensive availability of suitable high-altitude research sites. Furthermore, initial cost comparisons suggested that Ecuador may be a viable option. The expedition leaders then undertook a more detailed assessment of Ecuador's appropriateness, including the country's political climate, potential environmental hazards, notable seismic activity and proximity of sites to active volcanoes.

Javier Fernandez, Director of AndeanFace, served as the expedition's primary in-country contact during this phase, with multiple meetings held throughout July & August 2023. Several potential high-altitude sites were identified and investigated:

Left: Figure shows an altitude map of Ecuador with initial APEX 7 locations marked in blue. Adapted from Wikimedia Commons.

Bottom: Quito, Ecuador. Situated at an elevation of 2850m

- Whympet Hut, Chimborazo (5000m): This site had the desired altitude for research but was ruled out quickly due to being closed.
- Carrell refugio, Chimborazo (4800m): Suggested as an alternative for Whympet hut. While the altitude was deemed suitable, the maximum capacity was that of only 32 participants, insufficient for the desired APEX 7 participant numbers. Additionally, the ascent profile posed significant safety concerns, with a 2000m altitude gain from Quito to the refugio deemed too rapid for safe acclimatisation.
- Cotopaxi refugio, Cotopaxi (4800m): This refugio was identified as another suitable site, with a capacity that could accommodate the APEX 7 expedition. However, following discussions with the refugio manager, it was determined that exclusive booking of the refugio would be impossible, due to the high demand from climbers attempting the nearby Cotopaxi summit.

Considering these significant logistical challenges, Ecuador was ultimately determined to be an unfeasible location for the APEX 7 expedition.

Top: Refugio Whympet, Chimborazo
5000m

Left: Carrell refugio, Chimborazo
4800m

Right: Cotopaxi refugio, Cotopaxi
4800m

Bolivia

Following the exclusion of Ecuador, the decision was made for the APEX 7 expedition to return to Bolivia. This choice presented several strategic advantages, including institutional familiarity with the country from previous expeditions and an established network of in-country contacts.

In September 2023, the expedition leaders met with Jon Cassidy, Director of Bolivian Mountains, the logistics provider who had successfully supported the APEX 6 expedition. Jon's previous experience with the APEX 6 cohort provided a high degree of confidence in managing the complex transport and catering requirements of the full expedition.

Initial site selection in Bolivia involved a multi-site approach near refugio CasaBlanca (APEX 6 location). The proposed structure involved splitting the cohort across 4 neighbouring refugios, supplemented by a centralised geodesic-dome tent for communal meals and a dedicated laboratory building. However, subsequent collaboration with Bolivian Mountains highlighted major issues with this model:

- Administrative complexity: Each refugio was under independent ownership, requiring separate logistical and financial negotiations.
- Exclusivity: The refugio owners were unable to offer exclusive use of facilities to the expedition, requiring the facilities to stay open for mountain-tourists.
- Capacity and construction concerns: In-country reports suggested that one of the planned facilities was unlikely to be completed in time to accommodate the 100-person requirement.

Left: Figure shows an altitude map of Bolivia with final APEX 7 locations marked in blue. Adapted from Wikimedia Commons.

Right: Huayna Potosi Mountain

*Refugio Casablanca, Huayna Potosi
4800m*

An alternate refugio and expedition site was then explored, and a suitable refugio (Refugio Vista Panoramica) was found, which was located approximately 1 mile north-east of the initial site.

Refugio Vista Panoramica offered the expedition multiple strategic advantages:

- Capacity: Capable of accommodating up to 100 individuals within one refugio complex (across two buildings).
- Ascent profile: Suitable ascent profile from La Paz (similar to that of APEX 6), covering the 1200m elevation gain in approx 2-3 hours.
- Laboratory Infrastructure: Presence of a dedicated space that could be converted into a temporary laboratory building, located approximately 100 metres from Refugio Vista Panoramica.
- Emergency Access: Situated on a paved road allowed for 24/7 vehicle access for medical evacuations and equipment transfer.
- Dedicated to the expedition cohort: Exclusive booking of the refugio was possible.

*Refugio Vista
Panorámica,
Huayna Potosi
4800m*

3.4 Institutional Approval & Risk Management

Following country and site selection, a detailed expedition prospectus and associated risk assessment were created. The prospectus document outlined the expeditions objectives, personnel, detailed logistical plans, safety procedures, and a preliminary budget. Incorporated into the prospectus was a University Fieldwork Assessment Form (FA1), which provided initial hazard and risk identification and control measure summary. The prospectus and fieldwork assessment form were submitted to the University of Edinburgh Health & Safety Department to review, leading to formal health and safety approval for the expedition.

Alongside the prospectus, a comprehensive risk assessment was developed, which detailed potential hazards across all domains (including environmental, health, logistical and security) and outlining all harm-minimisation and mitigation strategies. This risk assessment was also reviewed and approved by the University Health and Safety Department and the University Insurance Office. Approval of the expedition prospectus and risk assessment were prerequisites for securing university insurance cover for all planned expedition and research activities.

It is noted that the University of Edinburgh Expeditions Committee, which previously streamlined approval for university-affiliated expeditions, is currently disbanded. Consequently, the established pathway used by prior expeditions was unavailable to the APEX 7 organisers. To navigate the new process, APEX 7 consulted with Professor Kate Heal, the former convenor of the Expeditions Committee, for guidance. The new process involved liaising directly with individual university departments, including the Health and Safety and Insurance department to secure the necessary approvals. While this caused significant challenges due to communication delays and further regulatory approvals, these were successfully overcome prior to the expeditions departure.

APEX 7 Expedition Prospectus 9117
07/06/2022

The University of Edinburgh Expeditions Committee

Request for expedition status: For this purpose an expedition is a group of two or more students travelling and carrying out research for a purpose. When the majority of participants are not University of Edinburgh students or recent graduates, the Committee can recommend that the expedition is approved but it will not be able to be called a University of Edinburgh Expedition.

All sections of the form should be completed. Sections can be requested APART FROM SECTION 7-9-5 which must not exceed 12 pages.

SECTION ONE: EXPEDITION DETAILS

1. NAME OF EXPEDITION: - Altimide Physiology: Expeditions (APEX) 7
2. EXPEDITION LEADER: Cameron Thomas & David Geddes.
Identification No: 0203987 & 02147139
3. ADDRESS OF EXPEDITION LEADER:
Name: Cameron Thomas
Email: cameron.thomas@ed.ac.uk
Name: David Geddes
Email: david.geddes@ed.ac.uk
4. LOCATION (Country Name) - Bolivia
LOCATION(S) (Pages Please) - La Paz & Realcema (Shimra Potosi Basecamp)
5. DATE OF DEPARTURE AND DURATION OF FIELD WORK:
Depart (dd/mm/yy) - 26/06/2022 (expedition formally begins 28/06/2022)
Number of weeks in the field - 2 weeks (12 days)

Key aspects of the risk management strategy for APEX 7 are covered on the following pages:

Environmental Hazards

Potential environmental hazards were assessed, considering the specific location (Bolivian Andes) and timing (June/July, winter, dry season) of the expedition. Key risks and mitigation strategies included:

- **Extremes of climate:** Operating at high altitude (up to 4800m) during winter months involved possible exposure to sub-zero temperatures, particularly at night. Mitigation involved providing participants with a comprehensive kit list specifying appropriate warm and waterproof clothing (Including sleeping bags rated comfortable to -10C) and emphasising layering (Appendix 1). Furthermore, expedition accommodation was adequately insulated. Logistical arrangements with Bolivian Mountains ensured 24/7 access to hot water, and thermal blankets procured in-country for additional needs.
- **UV radiation:** There is an increased exposure to UV at high altitude. The supplied kit list advised all participants to use SPF50+ sunscreen and lip balm, and to wear suitable clothing including sunhats and sunglasses. This advice was reinforced throughout the expedition during briefings. Furthermore, deliberate sunbathing was discouraged.
- **Natural disasters:** Risks such as avalanches, flooding, earthquakes and severe storms were assessed as low. This was based on the expeditions timing during Bolivia's dry season and the location of the basecamp being situated away from known avalanche or landslide areas. Although the risk was deemed low, emergency communications and evacuation procedures remained in place.

Top: Climate map of Bolivia. Adapted from Beck et al., *Scientific Data* (2023)

Left: Erythemal UV index with Bolivia marked in Blue. Adapted from CBS (2014)

Right: Climate graph of La Paz. Adapted from www.climate.top

Health & Medical Risks

In addition to the presence of four experienced expedition doctors, a detailed review and assessment of health and medical risks was conducted, with appropriate mitigation strategies implemented:

- Altitude Illness: Altitude illness was deemed to be one of the major risks associated with the expeditions location and objectives.
 - Prevention: A carefully planned phased-ascent profile was undertaken, involving 5 nights of acclimatisation in La Paz (3650m), before ascending to Huayna Potosi Basecamp (4800m) for 8 nights. This ascent profile, similar to that successfully used on APEX 6, underwent external review and received safety approval from Dr Jeremy Windsor, Director of the Centre for Mountain Medicine. All participants underwent pre-expedition medical screening by the expedition doctors to identify potential contraindications to high-altitude travel. Furthermore, the expedition doctors delivered a compulsory pre-expedition medical talk covering high-altitude illness recognition and prevention strategies.
 - Monitoring: Participants were monitored frequently throughout the expedition This included mandatory twice-daily symptom monitoring (including vital sign monitoring and Lake Louise Acute Mountain Sickness scoring). Furthermore, a buddy system was implemented which encouraged peer monitoring.
 - Management: The medical team possessed a comprehensive medical kit which contained equipment for high-altitude illness, including supplemental oxygen, and specific medications for altitude illness. Detailed evacuation plans were established for those with suspected severe altitude illness requiring descent. Rapid descent was the primary management strategy for severe altitude illness. Continuous (24/7) access to two vehicles & drivers was maintained throughout the expedition to enable evacuation if needed (approx. 1150m descent in 60min, appendix 2). Participants requiring further medical input were transferred to a pre-vetted tertiary medical centre, Clinica Cemes, in La Paz.

- **Travel-related illnesses:** Measures were taken to prevent common travel-related illnesses. Participants were advised to be up to date with routine UK immunisations and specific travel vaccinations. Discounted vaccinations were provided through two partner pharmacies in Edinburgh. Participants received detailed information in a medical information pack covering food and water safety, bite prevention, and management of minor illnesses. Strict hand-washing and hygiene measures were emphasised and facilitated to minimise the risk of gastrointestinal infections.
- **Dehydration:** Given the increased risk at altitude, participants were strongly advised to maintain high fluid intake throughout, and constant access to safe drinking water was provided.
- **Research procedure risks:** Potential risks associated with specific research activities were assessed and minimised by using appropriately trained personnel, employing aseptic techniques, and local anaesthesia where appropriate.
- **General medical cover and confidentiality:** All participants were required to have comprehensive medical insurance covering activities up to 5000m. All doctors maintained appropriate medical indemnity cover for their roles throughout. Appropriate medical confidentiality was maintained for all participants throughout, including secure handling of personal health information and access only by necessary medical personnel.

Travel & Transport Risks

Due to the expeditions significant international and in-country travel, a thorough assessment of risks and mitigation measures was undertaken:

- **International air travel:** Risks associated with international air travel were assessed as low but included flight disruptions (e.g. delays, cancellations) and extremely rare, major incidents. The expedition only used reputable airlines and participants were briefed on the importance of travel documentation and travel etiquette. Passport validity was checked prior to departure and comprehensive personal travel insurance was required for all participants.
- **In-country travel:** Travel within Bolivia involved using chartered coaches and vehicles. Mitigation of risks involved using a reputable established transport provider through the expeditions logistics partner, Bolivian Mountains. Participants were briefed on local road safety awareness and etiquette.
- **Equipment transport:** Specific transit insurance was arranged via the University of Edinburgh Insurance Department to cover research and medical equipment during international shipping and in-country transit.

Security Risks

The political security and country safety of Bolivia necessitated a detailed examination and discussion of security risks and mitigation measures:

- **Political instability:** Due to the frequent political unrest and riots in Bolivia, APEX 7 continually monitored the UK FCDO travel advice before and during the expedition. Furthermore, we maintained close contact with our in-country contact partner, Bolivian Mountains, for real-time updates.
- **Urban Safety:** Risks in La Paz included petty crime and theft. All participants were briefed on these risks and mitigation measures to reduce risk. Furthermore, a strict system was implemented to ensure volunteers did not explore La Paz on their own and were advised to travel in groups of at least four.
- **Support from the British Embassy:** APEX 7 had a direct line of communication with the British Embassy in Bolivia, including the Deputy British Ambassador, which allowed us to manage risks and have plans in place for emergency situations.

Operational and Logistical Risks

Due to the expedition's operational and logistical complexity, detailed attention was paid to:

- **Equipment Failure/Damage:** Due to the remote nature of the expedition, redundant equipment was brought to ensure backups were present for all essential equipment. Furthermore, equipment was split across multiple kit bags to minimise the damage if bags went missing. All critical scientific and medical equipment was transported in protective hard cases to and from the expedition to minimise the risk of damage during transit.
- **Data Breaches:** Only approved expedition personnel had access to any identifiable information, and all data was stored on an encrypted hard drive. Furthermore, a detailed Data Protection Impact Assessment (DPIA) was submitted and formally approved by the University of Edinburgh Data Protection Officer prior to the commencement of the expedition.
- **Financial Contingency:** Due to currency fluctuations in Bolivia, a sum of contingency money was taken on the expedition. This money was dedicated to any unforeseen costs related to expedition operations.
- **Communication Methods:** To mitigate the lack of cellular signal at our high-altitude refugio, the expedition purchased and set up a satellite communication device (Garmin InReach). In addition, select expedition personnel had limited access to the StarLink satellite system in emergencies. Furthermore, a dedicated mobile was purchased for the expedition, and all volunteers were made aware of the contact number.

Emergency Protocols

A detailed set of emergency protocols and flowcharts was designed, which were made available to all expedition committee members and doctors. These protocols detailed the steps and actions to be taken in the event of an emergency (e.g. participant evacuation, lost participant). Full emergency protocols and flowcharts can be found in appendix 3.

3.5 Logistical Operations

Equipment & Medical Kit

A comprehensive equipment manifest was created outlining for each item: quantity, whether it was to be flown out or purchased in-country, which bag(s)/case(s) it was to be packed in, weight, size, special handling requirements, value and owner. Each member of the organising team contributed items required by their specific projects, with the expedition leaders and doctors adding the remaining general logistical and medical equipment.

Manifests for each bag/case were also created, highlighting the contents of the case, and importantly, the worth and ownership of the items inside. These were translated into Spanish and sent to the British Embassy in La Paz, which forwarded them to several Bolivian government departments for pre-approval, namely: Dirección General de Migración (Border Control), Aduana Nacional (Customs), and Navegación Aérea y Aeropuertos Bolivianos (Civil Aviation Authority). Stamped copies, along with letters of support/ownership from supporting labs and companies, were carried both in the bag/case and on the individual responsible for the bag.

At the time of the expedition, Bolivia enforced a strict customs duty policy under which items with an estimated value exceeding \$10,000 (or the total value of all items imported by one individual, whichever came first) were subject to a 40% import tax. This was financially impossible for the expedition to cover, given an estimated total equipment value of \$500k to \$1 million. To avoid this, we worked with the British Embassy to provide 'proof of temporary importation' to the authorities mentioned above. Similarly, medical kit bags contained proof of purchase, prescriptions, and the GMC numbers of the medical team to avoid kit (particularly medications) from being seized at the border.

DIGEMIG
Dirección General de Migración

Aduana
Nacional

Expedition Transport

Due to the scale of the APEX 7 Expedition, organising suitable and affordable international transport was a primary objective for the organising committee.

Initially, the committee intended to secure group booking through a specialist group booking provider. Following multiple meetings with representatives from FlightCentre, a single group ticket for all volunteers was deemed infeasible due to two primary factors:

1. **Participant Flexibility:** Volunteers would have differing wishes/requirements for return flight locations and dates, to allow for personalised travel within South America after the end of the expedition.
2. **Prohibitive Costs:** Due to the limited routes into El Alto International Airport (La Paz), only two airlines (Avianca and Latam) provided suitable flight schedules. Quotations from these companies proved to be prohibitively inflated (up to 5 times greater than the standard rate).

To resolve this, the cohort was subdivided into four customisable flight groups, to balance logistical management and individual flexibility. Volunteers were free to choose any of the flight routes below:

1. Group A: Expedition + 2 weeks post-expedition travel (returning from Lima, Peru).
2. Group B: Expedition + 3 weeks post-expedition travel (returning from Lima, Peru).
3. Group C: Expedition + 3 weeks post-expedition travel (returning from Santiago, Chile).
4. Group D: Independent groups, subject to arrival criteria in La Paz.

Groups A-C were charged the same rate for flights further subdivided into groups of 9 for booking purposes. This strategy utilised a wide range of carriers and transit hubs to ensure affordability.

Figure shows the routes taken by APEX 7 volunteers for transport to La Paz, Bolivia.

All expedition volunteers were required to have a passport with at least 6 months validity after their scheduled return date.

Whilst in-country, ground transportation was organised and coordinated through our logistics partner, Bolivian Mountains. Coaches were chartered for all transport throughout La Paz and to/from Refugio Vista Panoramica, alongside two 4x4 vehicles for evacuations. A dedicated logistics truck was chartered for transport of expedition equipment to/from Refugio Vista Panoramica.

Expedition Shipping

Initially, the option of shipping both unused/non-consumable research equipment and samples back to the UK was explored. However, this proved prohibitively expensive, and in some cases impossible due to freight restrictions on lithium batteries or package size, so it was decided that only samples would be shipped home, with a committee member volunteering to fly back with the equipment instead.

The requirements and capabilities for sample shipping were as follows:

- Continuous chilled (0 to -10 degrees Celsius) storage
- Continuous deep-freeze (-80 degrees Celsius) storage
- Arrival to destination within 3 days.

A personal connection to DHL was used to secure shipping that fulfilled these requirements, as well as a £1000 charitable donation to the expedition. To process the request, DHL required the following details on the samples:

- Volume (including containers)
- Nature of contents
- Hazard level (UN code)
- Required maintenance temperature.

We completed several signed documents to allow samples to leave Bolivia and enter the UK, with DHL having an advisory role in how they should be filled out. These were:

- Customs Invoice (Bolivia)
- Customs Invoice (British)
- Certificate of Infection Status
- CDC Transit Letter
- Certificate of Responsibility
- Commercial Invoice.

Also required were manifests including the exact type and amount of the biological specimen, infection status, the fixing chemicals used, and the UN shipping code (indicating hazard level).

Samples were packed according to UN3373 and Packaging Guideline PI650 and stored on dry ice in styrofoam cool boxes before transport to DHL offices in La Paz. Passive temperature and leakage monitors were also placed inside each package to indicate whether samples had thawed and/or leaked at any point in transit. DHL topped up the dry ice in each package throughout the journey to maintain proper temperature. The destination address was the Institute of Regeneration and Repair (IRR) South Stores, where staff had been pre-informed and requested to keep samples at their indicated temperature until a member of the expedition team could move them to a permanent location.

3.6 Medical Team Selection

The selection of an experienced medical team was an essential part of expedition preparation and planning. Based on a total participant number of 100, it was decided that the expedition should have four expedition doctors, maintaining a 1:25 ratio. This number enabled 24/7 medical standby and the ability to maintain safety at basecamp should a doctor be required to accompany an evacuation.

A multi-disciplinary medical team was prioritised, aiming to recruit physicians with extensive experience in anaesthesia, emergency medicine, and general practice. Furthermore, clinicians were required to have prior experience in expedition, high-altitude, or event medicine. This ensured skilled coverage for high-altitude and expedition-related issues, as well as general medical issues.

The selection process utilised an open application form published on the [altitude.org](https://www.altitude.org) website to gather initial information and gauge interest. A total of 10 candidates applied, with 9 selected for interview. One applicant was excluded prior to the interview for unprofessional conduct and failure to respect the committee's student-led nature. Each remaining candidate underwent a one-hour interview with the expedition leaders, during which they were assessed and scored on their clinical expertise, high-altitude experience, and ability to integrate effectively into the expedition cohort.

Following these interviews, the four highest-scoring candidates were chosen as the expedition doctors, with one reserve. Due to one of the initial appointees no longer practising medicine in the preparation phases, they were substituted for the reserve candidate.

3.7 Expedition Sustainability

Acknowledging the potential environmental impacts of the APEX 7 expedition, the organising committee prioritised environmental awareness throughout the expedition's planning.

An ambitious plan was devised to offset expedition carbon emissions by establishing and maintaining an "APEX woodland". This plan developed significantly, and APEX 7 agreed to partner with a local tree supplier to help execute it. Unfortunately, communication with the environmental company partnered with APEX 7 ceased in the months leading up to the expedition, so the initiative could not be executed.

Despite these challenges, the committee increased discussions around expedition sustainability to ensure it remained a priority for operations and logistics. The expedition employed the following initiatives to reduce environmental impact:

- **Local Partnerships:** By partnering with Bolivian Mountains, APEX 7 was able to ensure that all financial investment remained within the host country. This included the hiring of local mountain guides, cooks, and drivers.
- **Water Supply:** To reduce reliance on single-use plastics, the expedition prioritised the use of bulk-bought water supplies, and participants were required to use reusable water bottles throughout the duration of the trip.
- **Waste Disposal:** A strict "leave no trace" policy was employed whilst at Refugio Vista Panorámica. All waste and refuse generated during the time at Huayna Potosi Basecamp were collected and transported back to La Paz for professional disposal. This included all medical waste, disposed of appropriately.
- **Medical Donations:** Following the end of the expedition, unused medical equipment and consumables were donated to local healthcare facilities in La Paz. This ensured resources were not wasted and not transported via international air back to the UK.
- **Offsetting:** All volunteers were provided with information regarding the environmental impact of their travel and were encouraged to explore carbon-offsetting schemes.

4. Expedition Research

4.1 Research Timeline

Initial Brainstorming and Development: 2023–2024

Research was a large focus of initial expedition planning. Initial brainstorming for potential research projects drew on previous APEX projects, identified gaps in altitude and hypoxia research, and reflected on personal experiences at altitude to develop research proposals. Throughout 2023 and 2024, the committee met with research supervisors and academic collaborators to develop and refine individual research project plans.

Data Management

Although APEX expeditions yield incredibly rich and valuable datasets, the absence of a centralised data management system across expeditions has resulted in issues with data accessibility and preservation. Dr Ian Maccormick, APEX 1 volunteer and APEX 6 supervisor, had recognised this as an issue and arranged for the APEX 7 Team to work with the UofE Digital Research Services (DRS) Internship Scheme to solve this challenge in anticipation of APEX 7.

APEX 7 worked with Clara Lopez Velasco over the summer of 2024 to identify the specific data management issues APEX faces and to create data management protocols (DMPs) for each research project. We met with relevant individuals within the University to identify potential suitable data repositories, ultimately choosing Edinburgh DataStore. Through working with the Edinburgh BioQuarter and Institute for Regeneration and Repair (IRR), we were fortunate to secure 100GB of space within the College of Medicine and Veterinary Medicine at no cost. This has allowed us to create a centralised, sustainable data management system which can be used for past and future APEX expeditions.

Data Governance & Approvals

Late 2024 was spent finalising the seven research elements which would encompass the APEX 7 Study. Each individual project's protocol and DMP were amalgamated to form the study protocol, alongside the other documents required for submission for study sponsorship and ethical approval. Study sponsorship from ACCORD (Academic and Clinical Central Office for Research and Development) was required prior to EMREC (Edinburgh Medical Research Ethics Committee) submission. Submitting the sponsorship and ethical approval was a major undertaking, taking most of December 2024 through April 2025 on an expedited pathway.

The final documents approved were as follows:

- EMREC Ethics Application
- APEX 7 Study Protocol
- APEX 7 Study Participant Information Sheet
- APEX 7 Study Consent Form
- APEX 7 Study Participant Recruitment Email
- APEX 7 Study Digital Questionnaires
- APEX 7 Expedition Risk Assessment
- APEX 7 Study GP Contact Letter
- APEX 7 Study Research Devices
- APEX 7 Study Data Management Protocols

We were granted initial EMREC approval on 23rd April 2025. Two non-substantial amendments were submitted prior to the expedition, with the second amendment being approved on the 2nd of July 2025.

Alongside working towards ACCORD sponsorship and EMREC approval, we secured device sponsorship and funding for many of the research elements. Notably, we applied to Medtronic's External Research Programme (ERP) and, as a result, obtained significant financial support and device provision for APEX 7 CORE.

Baseline Testing: May 2025

Baseline testing took place in the Royal Infirmary of Edinburgh Clinical Research Facility (RIE CRF), who were kind enough to support the study through provision of facilities and nursing support. Prospective research participants attended the CRF across a three week period.

Expedition volunteers were invited to participate in the APEX 7 Study via email with a copy of the study participant information sheet (PIS). If interested in participating in the study, they were invited to attend the CRF, where they had the opportunity to discuss any questions and self-screen for the study and specific research elements using the inclusion and exclusion criteria. If willing to participate as a research subject, they provided written consent to the APEX 7 Study. Basic physiological measurements and demographic data were collected alongside acute mountain sickness (AMS) scoring questionnaires. Further data was collected, such as blood samples and questionnaires, depending on specific research elements. Some samples were processed in the CRF, such as by centrifugation, and were safely stored in the CRF until they could be transferred to the APEX freezer in the QMRI.

Expedition: June/July 2025

Each day of the expedition had a meticulously planned timetable that encompassed both research requirements and other expedition activities. Significant disruption from lost baggage led to last-minute adjustments to data collection timings and to sourcing missing consumables (e.g., venepuncture equipment) in La Paz.

Basic physiological measurements (SpO₂, heart rate and temperature) alongside Lake Louise Score (LLS) and Visual Analogue Scale (VAS) questionnaires were completed bi-daily by research participants. Study-specific sampling occurred on various days throughout the expedition. Due to luggage delays, blood sampling for the HEAT and HBI study in La Paz was postponed to expedition day 6, just prior to ascending to Basecamp. The large majority of research sampling was conducted at Huayna Potosi Basecamp. The broad research timetable is illustrated on the following page.

Biological samples were stored temporarily on dry ice and then in a secure -80 degree freezer at Instituto SELADIS, La Paz. Samples were shipped back to the UK on dry ice with our courier partner DHL.

Post Expedition

Both NEU and SKIN required post-expedition data collection. Biological samples from the expedition were safely stored in the Institute for Regeneration and Repair and QMRI until transferred elsewhere for data extraction. We are now well underway with data analysis and write-up, with multiple projects aiming to submit for publication in mid/late 2026.

Expedition Research Timetable

Expedition Day	Location	Altitude	Study Requirements
Baseline	Edinburgh	Sea level	HBI, HEAT, eQTL, NEU, HiCORT, SKIN
Day 1	Arrival in La Paz 0000-1200	3640m	
Day 2	La Paz	3640m	
Day 3	La Paz	3640m	
Day 4	La Paz	3640m	
Day 5	La Paz	3640m	
Day 6	La Paz -> Huayna Potosi	4800m	HBI and HEAT (3640m), HiCORT (4800m)
Day 7	Huayna Potosi	4800m	HBI, HEAT, eQTL, HiCORT
Day 8	Huayna Potosi	4800m	eQTL
Day 9	Huayna Potosi	4800m	CORE
Day 10	Huayna Potosi	4800m	CORE, SKIN
Day 11	Huayna Potosi	4800m	CORE
Day 12	Huayna Potosi	4800m	
Day 13	Huayna Potosi	4800m	HiCORT
Day 14	Huayna Potosi -> La Paz	3640m	HICORT
Post-Expedition	Edinburgh	Sea level	SKIN, NEU

4.2 Research Projects

The broad aim of the APEX 7 study was to investigate the physiological responses to high-altitude-induced hypobaric hypoxia. A greater understanding of the impact of hypoxia and altitude on human physiology will allow further insight into altitude-related illness, such as acute mountain sickness (AMS), high-altitude pulmonary oedema (HAPE) and high-altitude cerebral oedema (HACE). Moreover, it will contribute to our understanding of how hypoxia affects critically ill patients at sea level, something which is often difficult to investigate due to multiple disease processes occurring simultaneously. The seven research project conducted on the APEX 7 expedition are as follows:

Accuracy and Stability of Pulse Oximetry Versus Arterial Blood Gas Analysis in Hypobaric hypoxia (N=58)

Led by Anya Tan, Cameron Norton and David Geddes, Supervised by Kenneth Baillie

APEX 7 CORE aimed to investigate the accuracy of pulse oximetry in hypobaric hypoxia. Pulse oximetry is a non-invasive method of assessing oxygenation in patients in clinical settings; however, inaccuracies have been reported under hypoxic conditions. Arterial blood gas sampling is the gold standard for measuring oxygen saturation. This study compared pulse oximetry measurements (SpO₂) with arterial blood gas measurements (SaO₂) under hypobaric hypoxic conditions. We received financial support from Medtronic and the provision of pulse oximeter devices through application to, and acceptance on, their External Research Programme.

eQTLs and Gene Expression in Hypobaric Hypoxia (N=75)

Led by Anya Tan, Supervised by Kenneth Baillie

Expression quantitative loci (eQTLs) are genomic variants which are associated with differential gene expression. Hypoxia is a complex trait where many genetic and environmental factors contribute to the disease state. Identifying eQTLs in high-altitude-induced hypoxia can help to understand the genetic risks associated with altitude illness, whilst also aiding understanding of disease susceptibility and severity in hypoxic and critical illness at sea level. This study added to the eQTL samples collected from APEX 4-6, increasing sample size and power, and allowing data analysis to begin.

The Impact of Acute Hypobaric Hypoxia on Daily Cortisol Profiles (N=4)

Led by David Geddes, Supervised by Nina Rzechorzek

APEX 7 HiCORT aimed to establish how 24-hour variation in cortisol at the tissue level was impacted by acute exposure and acclimatisation to hypobaric hypoxia. This was done using the U-Rhythm device, a pioneering ambulatory Microdialysis device that samples interstitial fluid at up to 20-minute intervals. Cortisol sampling in clinical practice is often time-consuming and logistically challenging due to variation in hormonal rhythms. The U-Rhythm device offered an alternative approach to this. Research subjects wore this device for 24 hours at three time points during the expedition to understand how cortisol dynamics operate under varying levels of hypoxia and altitude. Alongside this, high-resolution actigraphy monitoring and core body temperature monitoring was conducted to provide unparalleled resolution for daily rhythms at altitude.

Human Metabolic Adaptations in Hypobaric Hypoxia (N=20)

Led by Camille Maezelle and Ella McElnea, Supervised by Zoi Michailidou

Evidence from rodent studies suggests that hypoxia can increase thermogenic activity and white adipose tissue browning, thereby enhancing energy expenditure and metabolic adaptations. This study, in collaboration with the Michailidou lab at Nottingham Trent University, aimed to evaluate if similar mechanisms occur in human populations under naturally hypoxic conditions using blood sampling, questionnaires, and bioelectrical impedance analysis (BIA). Hypoxic exposure could potentially offer a novel and non-invasive approach to weight management and obesity treatment, advancing the field of metabolic medicine.

Investigating Dermatological Adaptations in High Altitude Environments (N=78)

Led by Colette Revadillo, Supervised by Sara Brown

The effects of altitude on skin barrier integrity are poorly understood, with high altitude potentially providing a natural, non-invasive means to improve skin barrier function by influencing hydration and trans-epidermal water loss (TEWL). APEX 7 SKIN investigated skin hydration and TEWL in participants with and without atopic dermatitis, using skin probe devices.

Markers of Neuronal Injury in Hypobaric Hypoxia (N=40)

Led by Anya Tan and Ella Andrea, Supervised by Andrew Sutherland

APEX 7 HBI investigated markers of neuronal injury at altitude, specifically GFAP (glial fibrillary acidic protein) and UCH-L1 (ubiquitin carboxy-terminal hydrolase L1). By sampling at three time points during the expedition, we aimed to investigate whether these markers changed in response to acute exposure to high altitude and hypoxia. The i-STAT Alinity and corresponding Abbott TBI cartridges allowed us to immediately analyse if GFAP and UCH-L1 were elevated in plasma samples.

Investigating Neutrophil Responses to Prolonged Hypoxia (N=16)

Conducted on behalf of the Walmsley lab, Supervised by Sarah Walmsley and Manuel Alejandro Sanchez Garcia

APEX has had a longstanding partnership with the Walmsley Lab, assisting with their investigations into changes in neutrophil lifespan, function, and gene activity under prolonged hypoxic exposure. APEX 7 contributed baseline and post-expedition samples to their ongoing research.

4.3 Research Reflections

APEX 7 was a complex, multidimensional study which certainly had both benefits and learning points from both a research and organisational point of view. The following is a personal reflection from the Head of Research, Anya Tan.

Research Scale and Power

The scale of the expedition certainly was an advantage in terms of increasing statistical power. This allowed us to be more creative with our research proposals during project development, as we weren't restricted by smaller sample sizes.

This scale however, had its logistical challenges. Coordinating a large multi-element study each with their own specific requirements (for example, fasted blood sampling) required significant thought and organisation, for both baseline testing and the expedition itself. Particularly in Bolivia, coordinating over eighty research participants across seven projects was difficult, especially when the expedition team is split across two sites.

Last Minute Adaptation

These challenges were compounded by multiple cases of lost research baggage on outbound flights. The study protocol required last-minute changes, so we adjusted the sampling days and research timings. Much of the first few days in La Paz were spent sourcing additional research supplies, such as venepuncture equipment, and hoping that the suitcase containing irreplaceable equipment (i.e., the Tempus tubes for the eQTL study) would appear before we ascended to Basecamp.

Although this seemed like a significant hurdle at the time, it definitely had some positives. For example, we now know that venepuncture equipment is relatively easy to source in-country. For future expeditions, this would certainly be beneficial as it would mean less shipping costs and continued work with local suppliers. Additionally, we have learnt that vacutainers meant for sea-level do not fill well at high altitude due to pressure changes, so this issue would be solved too!

Research Experience

We wanted to involve the volunteers in the research process as much as possible, out-with being research participants. During the expedition, we provided hands-on experience in data collection and processing across multiple studies. We led a venipuncture workshop and taught multiple volunteers laboratory techniques, such as centrifugation and pipetting. Volunteers were also trained to use the i-STAT Alinity and associated cartridges for the CORE and HBI studies. In addition to their research experience, our expedition doctors also organised informal teaching on ultrasound and provided guidance on careers in expedition medicine.

Final Reflections

It has been so rewarding to help introduce a new cohort of APEX volunteers to the fields of expedition medicine, scientific research, and altitude exploration. This expedition has been particularly memorable for the in-country connections we've built, including Dr Sosa at Instituto Seladis and the British Embassy. Post-expedition discussions regarding common research interests and future collaboration have already been promising.

From an organisational point of view, this study allowed significant personal and professional development for both myself and the other committee members. As an undergraduate student, it is rare to have so much autonomy in leading a study of this size. Experiencing the whole research process, in addition to the more unique challenges which come alongside the APEX expeditions, has been an invaluable experience. It certainly would not have been possible without the significant support, mentorship, and kindness of the many UofE staff members who helped us along the way.

"Please allow me to extend my warmest greetings. I am Dr. Luis Fernando Sosa Tordoya, Head of the Histocompatibility and Immunogenetics Laboratory of the SELADIS Institute, part of the Faculty of Pharmaceutical and Biochemical Sciences at the Universidad Mayor de San Andrés in La Paz, Bolivia."

It was a true honor and privilege, both for the SELADIS Institute and for me personally, to support Dr. Anya Tan and her dedicated team by providing ultra-low temperature storage of samples at -80°C, and to have contributed, even modestly, to the successful achievement of their research objectives during their expedition in Bolivia.

We sincerely hope that future expeditions from APEX and the University of Edinburgh will continue to carry out valuable research in high-altitude environments such as those found in Bolivia. Be assured that the SELADIS Institute and the Universidad Mayor de San Andrés will always remain fully willing and committed to offering the necessary support and collaboration to advance scientific research."

Luis Fernando Sosa T.

SELADIS Institute

Dr Sosa, Head of Histocompatibility and Immunogenetics (2nd from Left)

5. Expedition Volunteers

5.1 Volunteer Recruitment & Selection

Publicising APEX 7

The volunteer recruitment process began well before formal applications and interviews, focusing on elevating the APEX 7 profile through several strategic methods.

Social media, specifically Instagram, served as the primary platform for consistent engagement. By utilising the established APEX 6 account, the committee benefited from an existing following. Activity commenced in November 2023, providing a consistent stream of information regarding committee members, key dates, and the 'APEX Survival Guide', which was designed to illustrate the volunteer experience. We also shared significant updates, such as application deadlines and information sessions, through university year-group WhatsApp chats.

To broaden the reach beyond the current follower base, the committee identified relevant societies via the Edinburgh University Students' Association website. Outreach included medical, foreign language, geographical, and geological societies, most of which facilitated the campaign. Further engagement included 'takeovers' of the Edinburgh Medical School's official Instagram feed and stories.

Digital infographics were displayed on screens across the University, including the Jex-Blake Suite at the Royal Infirmary of Edinburgh and the Medical Education Centre at the Western General Hospital. Physical posters were also placed in these locations and the University Main Library. We used QR codes to provide streamlined access to additional information.

In-person recruitment included three information evenings held over an 11-month period to maximise interest. These sessions featured presentations from committee members on their specific roles and the research objectives of APEX 7. Alumni from APEX 6 also presented to provide a peer perspective on the expedition experience. Following these sessions, informal networking opportunities were provided to facilitate further discussion with the committee.

The committee also attended two Royal Medical Society fairs and the general University Freshers' Fair. We featured banners and QR codes to ensure accessible information, and we used the same setup during several afternoon sessions outside the Main Library.

In the pre-application survey, applicants were asked to identify their primary information sources, with multiple options permitted. As demonstrated below, word of mouth was the most frequent individual response, followed closely by the use of our Instagram account. This suggests that while social media is a highly effective recruitment tool, a diversified outreach strategy was essential to the successful acquisition of volunteers. Given that the majority of applicants identified two to three separate sources, it is difficult to isolate a single primary driver, reinforcing the value of maintaining multiple communication channels for future expeditions.

Volunteer Pre-Application

Pre-applications opened on 30 September and closed on 13 October. This phase was designed to ensure that those interested in attending APEX 7 were both eligible and logistically able to attend. The application also evaluated applicant awareness of APEX, motivations for participation, and perceived fit within the team. This process ensured that individuals progressing to the interview stage demonstrated a clear motivation and interest in the expedition. A full copy of the pre-application form can be found in the appendix 4.

Selection was conducted by two pairs of a single expedition leader and a head of volunteers working independently to prevent bias. We used a binary yes/no system for efficiency, given the volume of submissions. Applicant names remained redacted throughout the process to ensure impartiality. Following the independent reviews, the committee convened to discuss applicants who did not receive a unanimous consensus (i.e., those receiving Yes/No). We set a cap of 140 interview places before the review process to maintain rigorous selection criteria and keep the interview schedule manageable.

In total, 171 applications were received, with 138 individuals invited to interview, representing a progression rate of 80.7 per cent.

This pre-application methodology proved effective. The surplus of applicants demonstrated that the publicity campaign achieved its objectives, although the high volume presented an administrative challenge. The rapid review process facilitated operational efficiency, although it prevented an exhaustive analysis of minor differences between similar applications. While this prioritised selection speed and committee capacity, it necessitated a defined selection threshold to maintain administrative efficiency.

The blinded selection process in pairs was deemed the most objective and efficient method for progression. As many committee members are active within the Medical School community, blinding was the only way to ensure impartiality. We recommend using this methodology in future recruitment cycles to maintain the integrity of the selection process.

Interviews

Interviews commenced in November and were conducted daily from 6pm to 9pm over a four-week period. The schedule consisted of seven 25-minute slots per day, with each candidate interviewed by a panel of two to three committee members.

To manage the logistics for the 138 invited candidates, the committee used year-group-specific spreadsheets to allow self-selecting interview times. This decentralised approach significantly reduced the administrative burden on the committee. Although a single incident of unauthorised tampering with a spreadsheet required a temporary suspension of bookings and a formal reprimand, the method was highly efficient.

The recruitment process maintained high levels of candidate engagement throughout the transition from pre-application to formal interview:

- Confirmed interview attendances = 125 Candidates
 - Retainment from pre-application = 90.6%
- Actual attendance = 121 Candidates
 - Retention from initial confirmation = 96.8%
- Overall retainment rate = 87.7%

The committee prioritised fairness by ensuring that members did not interview candidates from their own academic year where possible. This was intended to reduce bias and ensure candidate comfort. Committee members were encouraged to use discretion and recuse themselves if they felt they were too familiar with a candidate to maintain an objective assessment, recognising the inevitable professional overlaps within the Medical School community.

The interview questions were designed to identify resilient, friendly individuals who possessed a strong understanding of the expedition's research focus (*Appendix 4*). The interview panel evaluated candidates across five categories, including an overall impression score. Each category was scored out of 5.0 and averaged to produce a final result. Candidates were then categorised using a colour-coded system to facilitate the final selection:

- **Red:** < 10.0
- **Orange:** 10.0 – 14.9
- **Yellow:** 15.0 – 19.9
- **Green:** > 20.0

While the selected cohort was consistently cooperative, post-expedition analysis suggested that the assessment of environmental resilience could be strengthened. Several volunteers struggled with minor logistical inconveniences, such as basic sleeping arrangements and cold showers, despite having been informed of the probable difficulties of high-altitude residency. Future selection processes should employ more explicit and rigorous methods to assess volunteers' capabilities to manage uncertainty and physical discomfort.

Another significant challenge encountered during the expedition was the administrative effort required to ensure volunteer compliance with research protocols. The committee frequently had to follow up with individuals regarding questionnaire completion and sampling attendance. To address this, future interviews should include a specific focus on research commitment to ensure that volunteers fully understand that fulfilling study obligations is of the utmost importance. While these adjustments may not fully eliminate compliance issues, they will help reinforce the expedition's scientific focus.

The scenario-based questions generally elicited positive results, particularly from those who later proved to be excellent volunteers. However, many responses were repetitive, suggesting that future questions should be more detailed or complex to encourage more unique and thoughtful perspectives. The inclusion of a non-academic question, such as the desert island scenario, proved effective for assessing a candidate's ability to think quickly under pressure and provided a platform for more informal, revealing conversation. While these critiques identify areas for technical refinement, the overall interview process was successful in securing a talented and eager volunteer group.

5.2 Volunteer Demographics

Places on APEX 7 were offered to 88 volunteers, with a reserve list of 9 individuals. Prior to the expedition, the cohort underwent several changes: four candidates withdrew, one was excluded during medical screening, and one offer was rescinded for failing to meet administrative deadlines. As a result, six candidates were moved from the reserve list to the primary cohort. Two subsequent withdrawals occurred after the final deadline and were not replaced. Following the tragic passing of one volunteer several weeks before departure, that position also remained vacant.

This section includes the demographics of our pre-application cohort and the demographics of our original 88 selected volunteers to accurately represent the selection process. It should be noted that gender-related data reflects gender expression rather than biological sex. These demographic figures exclude the eight members of the expedition committee.

Pre-application

Selected 88 volunteers

During the pre-application stage, 50 individuals identified themselves as potential Widening Participation candidates. These responses were recorded for the distribution of materials later in the recruitment cycle. Following interviews and offers, 23 potential WP volunteers were offered places on the expedition. Of this group, 18 individuals submitted a formal WP application, while five chose not to apply for the position. From the final pool of 18 applicants, eight positions were successfully allocated, and 10 candidates were unsuccessful. These 8 positions received a waiver of expedition fees.

5.3 Pre-Expedition

After selection of the volunteer cohort described above, the next phases concentrated on encouraging engagement, offering education and details about expedition expectations, and promoting group cohesion. This process involved collaboration across multiple initiatives.

A note on expedition communication

While earlier expeditions used Facebook Messenger as the main communication tool, the APEX 7 committee switched to WhatsApp for its user-friendliness and organisational features. This platform enabled the formation of several subgroups within the community and ensured everyone could access one another's contact information, which was essential for safety and logistical planning.

All formal or time-sensitive communications were prioritised via email. This approach established an official record of all interactions and ensured continuity, allowing any committee member to access and manage ongoing threads.

All communication challenges encountered were consistent with those of large organisations, primarily involving delayed responses or the misinterpretation of information. To mitigate these issues, it is essential that information be presented in a concise, structured format. Disseminating multiple unrelated or overly detailed updates simultaneously should be avoided to prevent information saturation. Additionally, it is recommended that internal deadlines be set at least 1 week before hard institutional deadlines to account for inevitable late submissions.

Pre-expedition activities

We aimed to cultivate a positive social atmosphere before the expedition through monthly socials and a dedicated Team-Building Day.

We organised activities such as pub trips, a wild swim at Portobello, and a BBQ in the Meadows. While attendance at these monthly events was not always high, the quality of socialisation was good. In our experience, this is common for university societies where established friend groups may be less inclined to attend unless the whole group goes. However, we were confident that the strongest foundations for teamwork would develop during the expedition itself.

The Team Building Day was our primary event, held shortly after volunteer selection. The morning was dedicated to research and logistical updates, followed by a bingo-style scavenger hunt around the city. To encourage intermingling across year groups and social circles, we grouped volunteers into 'families'. This successfully encouraged teamwork and camaraderie among people who were previously strangers.

The day also included a presentation by Jon Cassidy from Bolivian Mountains regarding post-expedition travel and the support his company could provide. This was a valuable session, and several volunteers later reported positive experiences after booking their travel through him. The event concluded with a pub quiz in the evening, providing a final opportunity for informal interaction before departure.

Reflections on pre-expedition

Overall, the pre-expedition team-building efforts were successful. Attendance was a recurring challenge, a common issue in university societies, but it didn't affect the quality of the connections formed during the expedition. Prioritising these opportunities is important, as even a few new connections among the cohort are valuable and rewarding.

A more significant challenge involved funding logistics; hosting nearly 100 individuals on a tight budget was difficult. Early in the planning stages, cash flow issues stemming from funding delays and rising living costs occasionally hindered the organisation of socials. This was not a reflection of the committee's financial management, but rather a result of external economic pressures.

The impact of rising costs was particularly evident when booking venues for social events. In previous years, it was often possible to secure bookings with minimal or no deposits. However, current economic conditions mean businesses are far less likely to offer discounts to charities or grassroots groups. Although increased funding would have been beneficial, these resource constraints encouraged creative solutions, and the team still managed to host effective events.

5.4 Reflections on the Volunteer Experience

The following sections are written from a first-person perspective by our heads of volunteers & wellbeing, Ella Andrea and Ella McElnea, who share some of their thoughts on how the volunteer experience was.

Wellbeing

Maintaining the mental and physical well-being of our volunteers was a priority, which the committee approached from several perspectives.

Drawing from personal experience on previous expeditions, it was recognised that an expedition like APEX involves significant stressors. Participants are far from their usual support networks, and the lack of home comforts can be challenging. Differences in infrastructure, customs, and food in the host country often lead to culture shock and increased anxiety.

To provide structured support, several committee members undertook mental health first aid training. This training informed the development of a mental health protocol shared with all volunteers (Appendix 5). This document outlined potential psychological challenges, provided mitigation techniques, and offered guidance on how to respond if issues arose, including clear escalation procedures.

Family and buddy systems were also introduced to facilitate peer support. Families were used to organise people for team building and other activities, ensuring volunteers had familiar faces beyond their initial social groups. This deliberate mixing helped create a wider network of connections within the cohort and reduced the impact of any local group tensions. The buddy system provided a more focused layer of support, pairing each volunteer with someone they did not previously know well for daily check-ins. This ensured every participant had a designated point of contact to flag concerns to the committee or medical team. This system proved effective, as it allowed for timely interventions when volunteers raised concerns about their buddies.

Room Allocations

Room allocations were carefully managed to ensure volunteers remained as comfortable as possible throughout the expedition. Given that the schedule was often very intensive, downtime was considered a valuable priority. To support this, the committee aimed to allow volunteers to select their own roommates wherever possible.

Initially, the entire cohort was intended to stay in a single hotel. However, due to changes shortly before departure, the group was split between two locations, just a short walk apart. While this arrangement was manageable, as the committee and medical team were divided evenly between the two sites. Maintaining the entire group in one location would have been preferable for both safety coordination and general camaraderie, though the split arrangement functioned adequately overall.

To organise the rooms, a form was distributed asking volunteers to nominate one or two preferred roommates, indicate a preference for single-sex accommodation, and provide any further relevant details. These preferences were followed as closely as logistical constraints allowed. The absence of specific complaints regarding roommate assignments suggests that this participant-led approach was effective.

The committee received some feedback on the hotel facilities, including the firmness of the beds and the availability of cold water for showers. These conditions were expected by the organisers and were generally accepted by volunteers with prior experience in similar travel environments. Although these amenities differed from standard domestic comforts, volunteers had been adequately informed of the expedition's conditions.

Collaboration with Expedition Medical Team

The Volunteer and Wellbeing team maintained a consistent presence by conducting regular 'rounds' to monitor participant welfare. Any identified issues were relayed to the medical team, and concerns were escalated as required. We followed up with internal committee briefings to reflect on specific situations and plan for future support needs.

Participants occasionally disclosed personal information, which was managed with a high degree of sensitivity. Following principles similar to those of patient confidentiality, the committee shared only the details strictly necessary with the relevant personnel. The medical team adopted a reciprocal approach, providing only the essential logistical context required for tasks such as quarantine or hospital transfers. This allowed the committee to maintain an effective support system without holding unnecessary sensitive data, helping to preserve their role as approachable peer supporters rather than clinical or authoritative figures.

Establishing a clear shared understanding of appropriate information flow between the committee and the medical team proved challenging during the initial stages of the expedition. Communication was initially overly cautious; while this prioritised privacy, it occasionally left committee members without sufficient context to assess the severity of specific situations or the need for escalation. This lack of situational awareness occasionally hindered the committee's ability to respond to enquiries from other volunteers or carry out their roles effectively.

For future expeditions, it would be beneficial to establish clearer protocols regarding what information should be shared, with whom, and at what level of detail. While participant confidentiality was our priority, a clearer framework would ensure all team members are appropriately informed to fulfil their operational responsibilities.

Activities in La Paz

During our time acclimatising in La Paz, we planned a range of activities to strengthen team bonds and give volunteers a chance to settle in. We drew on our experiences from APEX 6 while introducing some new ideas. Many of these activities were supported by Bolivian Mountains, as coordinating logistics for a group of 96 would have been extremely challenging to do independently. Their help with transport and bookings was invaluable.

We visited Valle de la Luna, which offered a unique landscape for the volunteers to explore in a relaxed setting outside the city. This provided a low-pressure environment for everyone to get to know one another before the more intense phases of the expedition. We also attended a local football match to see The Strongest, which was a highlight for many. The atmosphere was lively, and with almost every volunteer wearing a team shirt or scarf, it was a fantastic way to experience the local culture as a group.

Another standout activity was attending a Cholitas wrestling match, which offered a distinctive and memorable insight into local entertainment. We were also honoured to be invited to a reception at the British Embassy. This was a more formal experience that allowed us to represent APEX in a professional context and reflect on the expedition's goals. The staff were incredibly kind and accommodating throughout our visit.

Finally, we organised a family dinner night, during which volunteers went out in their assigned families and their committee 'parent'. This was designed to strengthen smaller peer connections and encourage socialisation in an informal setting before we headed up the mountain. This worked well, as the bonds formed within these families endured throughout the expedition.

Up the Mountain and Final Days

From previous experience, we understood that residing at altitude in a refugio would be challenging; it is not a particularly comfortable environment. It is cold, has low oxygen levels, can be crowded, and the sanitary facilities are frequently basic. However, we also knew that with the right support and mindset, it remains an incredibly rewarding experience.

Upon arrival, rooms were allocated on a first-come, first-served basis, as we did not have advance information regarding specific room numbers or bed configurations. We informed volunteers of the capacity of each room and asked them to tentatively organise themselves into groups of corresponding sizes. Rooms were then called out, and the first group to claim a space took the allocation. Given the limited information available beforehand, this was the most practical approach.

There was a noticeable variation in room quality, with some being significantly colder or less comfortable than others. For some volunteers, this likely impacted their overall experience, while for others it fostered resilience and a sense of camaraderie. While it would have been ideal for all rooms to be of a similar standard, there were still positives to the group's adaptation to the situation.

In hindsight, it would have been beneficial to frame these environmental challenges even more explicitly as part of the resilience and adaptability required for the expedition. Positioning these difficulties as central to the mission during pre-selection and interviews might have better prepared volunteers to manage their expectations during the most physically demanding phases.

In terms of well-being, our time on the mountain was occasionally very difficult. A number of volunteers experienced gastrointestinal issues, and several showed symptoms of Acute Mountain Sickness (AMS); ultimately, three individuals had to be evacuated back to La Paz due to illness. This was a challenging period for both the committee and the volunteer cohort. It was difficult to see people unwell, and equally taxing to provide support while committee members were often feeling unwell themselves or stretched thin by other responsibilities. We should have dedicated more thought to protocols regarding committee wellbeing for instances where the leadership team is also unwell, as this was one of the most challenging aspects of the expedition.

To maintain morale in a difficult environment, we planned a range of activities alongside our research commitments. We recognised that the committee would not have the capacity to lead all of these independently due to our workload, so we encouraged volunteers to take an active role in fostering a sense of community.

Prior to the expedition, we enquired whether volunteers would be interested in hosting clubs or activities, and the response was very positive. One standout example was a book club run by two volunteers. Many participants had purchased the book in advance, and it was excellent to see groups reading together and bonding over a shared experience. This had been a highlight for many on APEX 6, and we were pleased to see the tradition continue. Additionally, there were yoga sessions, quiz nights, card games, and a variety of other activities typical of a group entertaining themselves without internet access. With support from the refugio staff and Bolivian Mountains, we also organised a walk in the surrounding area. Having experienced this on APEX 6, we knew how memorable it could be, and it proved to be a highlight for many volunteers.

Although we could not always be as involved in every activity as we would have liked, it was important to us that the volunteers felt supported. As a small gesture, we brought cakes and birthday hats up the mountain to celebrate those who had birthdays during the expedition. This was greatly appreciated and allowed us to mark those moments in a meaningful way. The final night on the mountain was a standout moment of APEX 7. We held a large bonfire, sat together listening to music, and heard speeches from the committee and the medical team. We also held a small 'graduation' for one committee member and one volunteer who had missed their university ceremonies to attend the expedition. We danced late into the night, and it was a very special way to conclude our time at altitude.

After descending, the celebrations continued in La Paz. We held a group dinner at the hostel and hosted the "APEX Awards," which provided a lighthearted reflection on our experiences before we headed out for the evening. We had arranged to visit a local bar in advance, but they were unfortunately not well prepared for a group of our size. In future, it would be worth being even more explicit when communicating expectations to venues to ensure logistics run smoothly. One of the embassy staff kindly helped organise entry to a club, which worked out very well. Her guidance was invaluable, as we were not familiar with the local nightlife scene. It was an excellent conclusion to the expedition and a great opportunity to celebrate after years of planning and several weeks of intensive activity.

5.5 Volunteer Testimonials

The following are written testimonials from some of our APEX 7 volunteers:

"I think I can easily say that my time on APEX 7 was by far the most interesting experience I have had in my life so far. Having never left Europe, being shunted into La Paz at 3600m altitude was a shock the system, both physically and mentally. The team provided us with many opportunities to explore the different culture of Bolivia and take in its amazing landscapes. Being in the mountains for research was such a great time to disconnect and be surrounded by nature and good people. Beyond this, I was able to learn a lot from the expedition doctors about procedural skills like ABGs to ultrasound imaging and FAST scans. I was also given the opportunity to teach some of my medical knowledge to junior medical students, which was very fulfilling. An unforgettable experience I couldn't recommend enough!"

Cormac Morran, 5th Year, Medicine

"Partaking in APEX7 was an eye-opening experience. Coming from a non-medical background and only knowing one other volunteer, I wasn't sure what to expect but being immersed in the research side of medicine was incredibly interesting. I gained a deeper understanding of how critical data collection, analysis, and fieldwork are to improving healthcare worldwide. A highlight was observing and even taking part in several impromptu skills sessions, from expedition doctors teaching us how to use a portable ultrasound to being allowed to take blood from a very generous committee member! The standout, however, has been the lasting friendships and genuine connections that have made the experience truly unforgettable. This expedition not only deepened my appreciation for a previously unfamiliar field but also sparked a love for the outdoors and future exploration."

Oscar Helliwell, 4th Year, Finance & Business

“One of the most intense but rewarding experiences I’ve ever had was being a part of the APEX 7 expedition to Bolivia. Alongside the other volunteers, I took part in the high-altitude research projects studying how the body responds to extreme elevation. Living in basic accommodation up the mountain with no phone signal or internet took some adjusting, but it also helped us all disconnect and really focus on the experience. I learned so much about how altitude affects the body – both in myself and in others – and it gave me a new appreciation for how resilient humans are. What really made the trip, though, were the people. Being surrounded by such a driven, like-minded group created a strong sense of community, and I left with many new, but genuine friendships. It was challenging, eye-opening, and an experience I’ll never forget.”

Robyn Ward, 5th Year, Medicine

“My APEX 7 experience was incredible and something that I will always look back on as a true highlight of my university experience. I formed close friendships with some amazing people I might never have otherwise met and created lifelong memories with them, both in our time on expedition and travelling afterwards. In particular, the last night up Huayna Potosi where we danced (breathlessly!) with the bonfire is a memory I will forever cherish. I am grateful also to have had the experience of being involved in research. It really brought to life things that we read about in papers and textbooks every day at university, so has given me a real appreciation of how much work goes into creating evidence and guidelines that we are taught to follow. I am very grateful for the experience I had on APEX 7 and thank you to everyone who made it happen!”

Amelia Aves, 2nd Year, Medicine

““The APEX7 expedition was an amazing opportunity. Having never travelled before, it was a completely new experience in a new culture, as well as carrying out research. The whole expedition gave me so many learning opportunities, both academically and personally. Assisting with the research data collection gave insight into the protocols that need to be followed to obtain accurate results and preserving the samples to be transferred back from the isolation of the mountain to the lab in Edinburgh. Personally, spending time at this altitude was tough, and I think we all felt the effects on our bodies, but the sense of community the expedition brought made this much easier. The expedition was run extremely well, and I felt safe and cared for at all times, with plenty of food as well as medical assistance on stand-by if need be. It was an amazing opportunity that I miss constantly.”

Zack Swales, 3rd Year, Medicine

6. Expedition Finances

6.1 Expedition Funding

Between October 2023 and March 2025, the Funding, Grants and Sponsorship (FGS) team applied to 16 grants, identified as suitable from a total of 49. These included internal University grants opportunities as well as a range of UK-based and international charitable organisations. Grants identified and applied to were related to the fields of expeditionary medicine, Scottish culture, and mountaineering.

Of the 16 grants applied for, 3 were successful, gaining a total of £9,848 in grant funding for the expedition. This was composed of the following:

- £5,000 from the University of Edinburgh's Student Experience Grant
- £2,956 from the Souter Charitable Trust
- £1,892 from the Scottish Mountaineering Trust.

In addition to these grants, we were generously supported by a one-off grant of £10,000 from the University's College of Medicine and Veterinary Medicine and a one-off donation of £3,270 from the APEX charity. This led to a total grant and funding supply from the funding, grants and sponsorship side of the expedition of £23,118.

The FGS team focused on grants for the expedition as a whole and was not responsible for funding each research project, each of which had its own internal budget managed by the respective research lead. The largest support to expedition research was received from the medical technology company, Medtronic, as part of their External Research Programme initiative. Medtronic provided £22,891 of support to the APEX 7 CORE study and associated expedition costs (see more in section 4).

Despite the above, the most significant individual source of funding for the expedition was internal, from volunteer contributions. Each volunteer was charged a total of £350 for expedition contributions, roughly matching the support received from external sources.

Throughout the preparatory stages, a key aim for the FGS team was to keep costs as low as possible for expedition volunteers. It was decided to avoid volunteer contributions covering costs related to research consumables and research logistics, only expedition logistics and consumables.

Due to the support of the above grants, the APEX 7 expedition were able to subsidise expedition contribution costs for 8 of the expedition volunteers from widening participation backgrounds (as defined by the University of Edinburgh criteria). This initiative was undertaken to make the expedition as accessible as possible to students for whom finances would otherwise be a barrier. A total of 18 volunteers applied for the widening access positions, and the 8 allocated positions were allocated at random out of those who applied.

All expedition finances were managed through a dedicated Bank of Scotland Business Bank account with the expedition leaders as co-signatories.

See below for a summary table of grants applied to by the APEX 7 FGS team and their outcomes:

Grant	Grant	Amount (£)	Notes
EUSA Development Fund	Rejected	0	Rejected due to previous support for APEX 6
UoE Student Experience Grant	Accepted	5000	Student experience focused
Jeremy Willson Charitable Trust	Rejected	0	Rejected due to previous support for APEX 6
Scientific Exploration Society	Rejected	0	High volume of applicants. Application did not cover research projects adequately
Captain Scott Society Spirit of Adventure Award	Rejected	0	High volume of applicants
Scottish Mountaineering Trust	Accepted	1892	Provision for medical supplies
WMS Houston Grant Project 1	Rejected	0	Applications for HEAT project. Positive feedback, but not sufficiently competitive
WMS Houston Grant Project 2	Rejected	0	Applications for HiCORT project. Positive feedback, but not sufficiently competitive
WMS Houston Grant Project 3	Rejected	0	Applications for eQTL project. Positive feedback, but not sufficiently competitive
Explorers Club - Rolex Grant	Rejected	0	High volume of applications
Jeremy Willson Charitable Trust (reapplication)	Rejected	0	Rejected as scale of 100 participants too large for support
Souter Charitable Trust	Accepted	2956	Challenging to communicate with. Had to chase heavily for outcome and to receive money
Ponton Trust	Rejected	0	Application not relevant to trust
Transglobe/Ralph & Ginny Fiennes Award	Rejected	0	Grant decommissioned.
Mount Everest Foundation	Rejected	0	No financial support due to reduced resources, prioritising research in rarely visited regions
Captain Scott Society Spirit of Adventure Award (reapplication)	Rejected	0	High volume of applicants

6.2 Income & Expenditure

The total income for the expedition was £198,997.60, and the total expenditure was £196,332.33. See below for a full budget for the APEX 7 expedition. Note - This budget includes pending payments. This does not include budgets for individual research projects which are not included in this report.

SUMMARY		
Income	£	198,997.60
Expenditure	£	196,332.33
Net	£	2,665.27

INCOME	
Description	Amount
Expedition Contributions	
Volunteer Contribution	£31,000.00
Committee Payments	
Committee Contribution	£3,200.00
Committee Flights	£3,396.82
Temporary Float	£3,000.00
Flight Payments	
Volunteer Flights	£100,934.85
Grants & Sponsorships	
EUSA Student Experience Grant	£5,000.00
Scottish Mountaineering Trust	£1,892.00
College of Medicine & Veterinary Medicine	£10,000.00
Medtronic External Research Programme	£25,704.00
APEX Charity	£3,270.00
Souter Charitable Trust	£2,956.00
DHL	£1,000.00
HiCORT Project Support	£1,575.50
Misc	
Expedition Jackets	£5,100.00
Equipment Payments	£78.00
Product Refunds	£145.45
Flight Refunds	£744.98
Total	£198,997.60

EXPENDITURE	
Description	Amount
Logistics	
Bolivian Mountains Logistics	£48,836.80
Volunteers	
Deposit Refunds	£500.00
Independent Flight Refunds	£10,400.00
Equipment Refunds	£22.75
Misc Refunds	£1,345.57
Widening Access Places	£2,800.00
Teambuilding Costs	£224.20
Flights	
Flight Tickets	£99,002.71
Baggage Costs	£2,430.00
Expedition Equipment & Supplies	
Team Jumpers	£2,587.20
Team Jackets	£7,770.00
Peli Cases	£249.97
Van Hire	£253.00
Soft Bags	£182.95
Misc Supplies	£157.98
LHR Hotel	£406.25
Research Equipment & Supplies	
General Equipment	£2,119.02
Clinical Research Facility	£264.72
Core Temperature Monitoring Capsules	£1,015.85
HiCORT Consumables	£1,575.50
Printing Costs	£112.25
During Expedition Costs	
International Minutes	£20.00
Abroad Card Fees	£6.82
Cash Withdrawals	£1,274.42
Dry Ice	£70.00
Sample Shipping VAT	£143.92
Medical Team & Supplies	
Doctor Payments	£8,634.89
Medical Supplies	£859.04
Misc	
Temporary Float Refund	£3,000.00
Bank Account Admin Fees	£38.67
Sattelite Telephone Fees	£27.85
Total	£196,332.33

6.3 Grant Funding Landscape

Raising funds for APEX 7 occurred within an increasingly challenging funding landscape. Several grants that supported previous APEX expeditions were found to be inactive or has transitioned away from financial support of expeditions. Unsuccessful grant applications frequently cited record-high applicant volume, heightened competition among high-quality proposals, and reduced available funding pools. Furthermore, the sponsorship avenues that had previously been successful for other expeditions were no longer viable, as other companies faced financial challenges and were unable to sponsor projects.

A significant challenge involved distinguishing APEX 7 as a unique, separate entity to organisations that had supported previous APEX expeditions. Additionally, some early applications were unsuccessful due to poor alignment with specific grant criteria or insufficient detail in the applications. This was notably prevalent with applications made in earlier stages of planning APEX 7.

To ensure the viability of future expeditions, organisers should pivot away from general expedition-related grants towards higher-value research-linked financial support. While this approach offers a more stable funding source on a larger scale, it necessitates the early development of research projects to strengthen applications. Future expeditions must also be prepared to manage the increased legal and administrative burden associated with such high-level corporate partnerships.

6.4 Surplus & Future Expenses

With a total incoming of £198,997.60 and outgoing of £196,332.33, there remains an excess of £2665.27 (*including pending*). The excess remaining will be used by the APEX 7 expedition team for ongoing analysis and presentation of our research studies. For example, we hope to use some of these funds to present at upcoming conferences.

Grant Name	Funding Source	Start Date	End Date	Status	Notes
Grant 1	ABC Corp	01/01/2023	31/12/2023	Active	Grant approved for funding.
Grant 2	DEF Org	01/01/2023	31/12/2023	Completed	Grant completed successfully.
Grant 3	GHI Foundation	01/01/2023	31/12/2023	Rejected	Grant not approved due to budget constraints.
Grant 4	JKL Trust	01/01/2023	31/12/2023	Pending	Grant application under review.
Grant 5	MNO Charity	01/01/2023	31/12/2023	Active	Grant approved for funding.
Grant 6	PQR Foundation	01/01/2023	31/12/2023	Completed	Grant completed successfully.
Grant 7	RST Trust	01/01/2023	31/12/2023	Rejected	Grant not approved due to lack of detail.
Grant 8	UVW Charity	01/01/2023	31/12/2023	Active	Grant approved for funding.
Grant 9	XYZ Foundation	01/01/2023	31/12/2023	Completed	Grant completed successfully.
Grant 10	ABC Corp	01/01/2023	31/12/2023	Active	Grant approved for funding.
Grant 11	DEF Org	01/01/2023	31/12/2023	Completed	Grant completed successfully.
Grant 12	GHI Foundation	01/01/2023	31/12/2023	Rejected	Grant not approved due to budget constraints.
Grant 13	JKL Trust	01/01/2023	31/12/2023	Pending	Grant application under review.
Grant 14	MNO Charity	01/01/2023	31/12/2023	Active	Grant approved for funding.
Grant 15	PQR Foundation	01/01/2023	31/12/2023	Completed	Grant completed successfully.
Grant 16	RST Trust	01/01/2023	31/12/2023	Rejected	Grant not approved due to lack of detail.
Grant 17	UVW Charity	01/01/2023	31/12/2023	Active	Grant approved for funding.
Grant 18	XYZ Foundation	01/01/2023	31/12/2023	Completed	Grant completed successfully.
Grant 19	ABC Corp	01/01/2023	31/12/2023	Active	Grant approved for funding.
Grant 20	DEF Org	01/01/2023	31/12/2023	Completed	Grant completed successfully.

7. Expedition Execution

7.1 Expedition Itinerary

The APEX 7 expedition followed a 16-day in-country structure, split into 3 distinct phases: Initial acclimatisation in La Paz, ascent to a high-altitude sojourn, descent to La Paz and the end of the expedition. The expedition structure enabled a controlled ascent to altitude, with time for acclimatisation and subsequent research.

A - Expedition Travel

26th June 2025 - 27th June 2025

On the 26th of June 2025, members of the APEX 7 expedition met at London Heathrow Airport to begin travel to South America. Due to the size of the cohort and post-expedition travel, participants were divided into several flight groups, with departures throughout the day. Expedition organisers were present throughout this stage to assist with volunteer check-in and baggage drop-off.

Transit to La Paz involved itineraries lasting between 24 and 48h hours, transiting through major hubs including Madrid, Paris, Bogota and Montreal (See expedition transport section). All volunteers arrived in La Paz within a set arrival window of between 00:00 and 12:00 on June 28th to ensure the expedition remained on schedule.

B - Acclimatisation

Expedition days 1-5

28th June 2025 - 2nd July 2025

Following arrival in La Paz, volunteers spent five days (six nights) acclimatising at 3,600m. This period was crucial for volunteer wellbeing and essential for identifying early signs of altitude illness. The team was split between Hotel Sajama and Hotel Isabella, which are approximately a 2-minute walk apart. Hotel Sajama served as the expedition's central hub. Approximately two-thirds of the expedition resided at Hotel Sajama, and one-third at Hotel Isabella. Breakfast was provided at Hotel Sajama for all volunteers, and all briefings/research were conducted in the hotel's dedicated expedition communal space.

This phase also allowed initial research procedures and sample collection, notably venepuncture for APEX 7 HEAT. In addition to research commitments, the expedition committee organised multiple events to encourage socialisation and cultural exploration, including:

- A formal reception at the British Embassy for the full expedition, attended by the Deputy British Ambassador
- Cultural visits to the Valle De La Luna and a local "Cholita Wrestling" event
- Attendance at local football match (*The Strongest vs Universitario de Vinto*)
- Organised expedition "family" team dinners

C - Ascent & High-Altitude

Expedition Days 6 - 14

3rd July 2025 - 11th July 2025

Following acclimatisation, the expedition ascended on the 3rd July to **Refugio Vista Panoramica** at the Huayna Potosi Basecamp (4,800m). The team remained at this altitude for **eight nights, until 11th July**.

The volunteer cohort was split between two adjacent refugio buildings to manage capacity, with roughly half of the expedition in each building. All meals and supplies were provided to volunteers throughout this phase, including accommodations for specific dietary requirements.

Daily testing was conducted in a dedicated laboratory building at this altitude. A typical day at high-altitude was composed of:

- 06:30 - 08:00: Fasted physiological measurements and blood samples
- 08:00 - 09:00: Breakfast and completion of expedition questionnaires
- 09:00 - 12:30: Morning research block for specific studies
- 12:30 - 14:00: Lunch
- 14:00 - 18:00: Afternoon research block for specific studies
- 18:00 - 20:00: Evening Meal and completion of expedition questionnaires
- 20:00 - 23:00: Research data-entry and volunteer free time

D - Descent & Post-Expedition Travel

Days 15 - 16+

12th July - 13th July (+)

Following the successful completion of all research objectives at 4800m, the expedition cohort descended back to La Paz on **11th July**. This was followed by a two-night stay in La Paz to finalise research commitments and host an end-of-expedition social event. The APEX 7 expedition formally concluded at **00:00 on 13th July 2025**, at which point volunteers were free to begin their independent **post-expedition travel**.

During this final in-country phase, the expedition organising committee coordinated the management and shipping of all expedition equipment and assets:

- Biological Samples: All biological samples collected during the 16-day period were packaged and **shipped back to the UK** via DHL cold-chain services for further analysis
- Equipment: Research equipment and medical supplies were inventoried and returned to the UK
- Data and Miscellaneous: Final versions of digital datasets were backed up and secured. Committee debriefings took place to ensure the completion of all expedition goals before the expedition's conclusion

E - Data Analysis & Dissemination

13th July - Present

The **final phase** of APEX 7 is ongoing. This phase focuses on the transition from raw field data to academic contributions. The following tasks are being undertaken:

- Biological sample processing and analysis.
- Manuscript production for all research studies.
- Presentation and dissemination of research findings.

Furthermore, the expedition committee continues to oversee the project's finances, including management of outstanding research and logistics payments. The final phase of the APEX 7 expedition is expected to be completed by the end of 2027.

7.2 Expedition Operations

7.2.1 Gear Collection & Travel To Heathrow

Over the months preceding the expedition, equipment was collected and centralised in one location in Edinburgh. The medical kit was collected, packed into a dedicated emergency response bag and extra duffel before being sent down to one of the expedition doctors in England for them to fly out with. Four days before departure, equipment was packed according to the manifests, ensuring that essential supplies were split across multiple bags in case of damage or loss. Careful thought was given to how 'flight restricted' items such as lithium-based batteries and sharps were packed. Laptops and other small electrical devices were placed in hand luggage where possible; larger devices containing batteries were placed in cases, no sharps in hand luggage. Airline approval for carriage of lithium batteries in the hold of the plane was sought weeks in advance of flying – this was achieved by classifying devices as 'essential medical equipment'. Bags and cases were secured with TSA approved locks and had GPS trackers placed inside.

In the early morning of the 25th of June, the Expedition Leaders packed a rental van and set off to London Heathrow, making 2 stops – one to pick up the Head of Research and another to collect HiCORT research equipment. The Crowne Plaza Heathrow T3 hotel was used as a base for equipment and four members of the team overnight, to facilitate easier transport of equipment to the terminal. On the morning of the 26th, the Expedition Leaders returned the van in central London and collected the expedition's cash US Dollars (for the final Bolivian Mountains payment) before heading back to Heathrow before departure.

7.2.2 Departure from UK & Arrival To Bolivia

Volunteers

Members of the organising team were present at check-in for each flight group to ensure that all volunteers had arrived and had their required documents, and to distribute both expedition jackets/fleeces that were not picked up in Edinburgh and some wearable research devices. Volunteers were warned that we might need to place some research equipment in their bags, but this was ultimately avoided.

All flight groups otherwise departed with no concerns and arrived in La Paz on time.

Despite Bolivian border control (Direccion General de Migracion) being informed of our arrival as a research expedition, volunteers were advised not to wear APEX-branded apparel when transiting through immigration at La Paz to avoid extra questioning. All team members entered Bolivia without issue.

The expedition leaders met Jon and Miriam from Bolivian Mountains in the LPB arrivals hall to coordinate the transport of volunteers and equipment to Hotels Sajama and Isabela. Two coaches, arranged by BM, were utilised, running two round trips each due to the staggered arrivals of volunteers in La Paz. Half of the committee went on the first trip, so that room arrangements (see Volunteers section) could be facilitated; the remaining committee members stayed in LPB to welcome arriving volunteers from the second flight route.

Equipment

Initially, we had planned to split research bags and cases among several committee members to avoid excessive extra baggage costs and questions at Bolivian customs regarding the 'import' value of our equipment (individuals have a \$10,000 total limit before being required to pay tax). However, it was ultimately decided that two members of the committee should take responsibility for all research luggage. The justification was that it would be easier to import the equipment under one or two names and have them deal with the Bolivian authorities, as the process can be complex, leaving other committee members free to continue with other aspects of the expedition.

Unfortunately, we ran into multiple issues at check-in. Despite pre-approval from both AirFrance and Avianca, check-in agents at Heathrow were concerned about the lithium-ion batteries being transported in the aircraft's hold. A lengthy discussion took place regarding their use as medical devices/equipment, and we were eventually given a temporary pass for the flight to CDG, but we needed full approval from AirFrance upon arrival in Paris. Full approval was granted by AirFrance after they were provided with technical literature for the equipment, which demonstrated its intended use and battery capacities. Miscommunication at Heathrow also meant an additional baggage charge was paid at CDG, as the first one covered only the LHR to CDG leg.

Upon arrival in La Paz, we discovered that over half of all research bags/cases had not arrived (our GPS trackers reported them in Paris, Bogota and Santiago), along with many of the volunteers' personal bags. This became a prominent, ongoing problem throughout the expedition. Despite our best efforts to distribute equipment among bags, some essential equipment was found only in bags that went missing. Communication channels with Avianca and AirFrance were initiated immediately through airport staff at LPB, and all pieces of luggage were eventually recovered after much back and forth. However, many of these bags arrived late into the expedition, requiring us to purchase additional research consumables in La Paz and some extra clothing/equipment for volunteers. Avianca were very helpful throughout the entire process, discovering and rectifying the handling errors made by AirFrance in Paris. AirFrance denied any and all responsibility for the problem, even when handed irrefutable evidence, and failed to provide compensation. Expedition insurance claims were unfruitful, but volunteers had success with personal claims.

7.2.3 La Paz Acclimatisation & Activities

Room arrangements were preorganised by the Volunteers and Wellbeing team to speed up the process when in-country, but this still proved very chaotic. Volunteers were informed of a mandatory morning briefing scheduled for the next morning, both verbally and via the expedition WhatsApp announcements chat, before being allowed to head to bed.

This briefing was the first meeting of the whole team in La Paz and included a rundown of the pre-ascent research timetable, tips for exploring the city and staying safe, expected behaviour, and, importantly, a 'this is how you may feel right now' medical talk from our doctors. We continued with a quicker, but still mandatory, meeting every morning of the expedition, highlighting the research goals for the day and any key updates.

During the acclimatisation period, the committee began completing the planned tasks on our internal timetable. This included: unpacking and setting up research equipment required, placing signage (handwashing reminders, research timetables...) around both hotels, setting up the research LAN and network attached storage, setting up observation monitoring stations, letting emergency contacts know of our safe arrival, recon trips to the mountain refugio/lab, and calming volunteer concerns.

We liaised with Bolivian Mountains regarding: where to obtain dry ice and oxygen, standard freezer storage for samples, research contacts at local universities for -80 degree celsius storage.

Our medical team made an initial visit to our chosen hospital to collect sharps containers and discuss treatment plans for potential scenarios. We also spent considerable time acquiring replacements for equipment lost in transit, namely venepuncture equipment and Vacutainer EDTA tubes, so that sample collection could start as soon as possible.

The volunteer and wellbeing team focused on facilitating the pre-planned activities in La Paz through arranging transport and tickets with Bolivian Mountains.

On the recon trip to the refugio/lab, it became clear that there would simply not be enough space for all the volunteers with the then-current sleeping setup. The expedition leaders discussed potential options for the Bolivian Mountains, and it was decided that we would try to compact sleeping areas and replace some beds with bunk beds where possible. This was in no way ideal and led to cramped living quarters, but we deemed it preferable to having a large contingent of the expedition in a tent encampment away from the main hut.

7.2.4 Ascent To Basecamp

In the evening on the day before the ascent, the committee and medical team gave a pre-ascent brief outlining the plan for the following morning. This was similar in content to the arrival brief and covered tips to stay healthy and safe, expectations of behaviour, research plans, and medical red flags.

Most research equipment was packed the night before, but daily observation equipment had to be packed after morning sample collection. Likewise, for some HiCORT equipment. Despite this, the ascent began on time, with a convoy of 4 coaches and 2 4x4s carrying the team and equipment (including oxygen cylinders, a chest freezer, and dry ice).

Similar to La Paz, rooms were allocated by the Volunteers and Wellbeing team. This was done in-the-moment, as we were unsure what exact provisions would be available until we arrived. The expedition doctors chose a central room in the main hut as their dedicated medical space and hung curtains to create private consultation areas. Two doctors slept in this room overnight, acting as the 'on call' team whilst the 'off' team slept in tents close by.

7.2.5 Life At Basecamp

Research activities up the mountain were split between the common room of the main refugio (used for morning observations, occasional venepuncture, and overnight monitoring) and the dedicated research hut (used for most venepuncture, sample storage and analysis, and ABGs), located a 5-minute walk uphill. We ensured the research hut had adequate space, watertight roofing, power, lighting, and heating installed on the recon trip.

Timetables indicating participant numbers, calling time, and the location of sample collection were placed in the main refugio, the annex, and the research lab. Despite this, we still had trouble getting volunteers to arrive on time, so we often needed to find individuals and bring them to the lab.

Dry ice stores were replenished halfway through the stay up the mountain, along with food and water, by the Bolivian Mountains team. Samples that required -80 storage were taken down to Instituto Seladis on these runs by the Head of Research.

We strived to include volunteers in research activities where possible. This was typically sample processing and analysis after some training had taken place.

For the most part, volunteers were left to arrange their own activities, with the committee planning a few nights of entertainment. Strict rules were put in place, alongside a logbook that volunteers needed to use if they planned to take an excursion away from the refugio, noting who was leaving, the time of departure, the estimated time away, and where they were heading. Swimming, strenuous exercise and further ascent in altitude were banned for research and safety reasons. Hygiene was preached as the single most important factor volunteers needed to pay attention to, with hand-washing facilities (soap and water) available in all toilets, at the doors to the dining area, as well as hand-sanitiser stations and signage placed everywhere.

As in La Paz, a brief took place each morning (and occasionally in the evening before intense research days), highlighting the day's main research, available activities, and, if dedication seemed to be slipping, occasionally reminding volunteers of their responsibilities on the expedition.

Missing persons and search-and-rescue protocols had been developed and signed off by the University of Edinburgh, the Bolivian Mountains, and the expedition doctors. Emergency decision-making was shared between the leaders, with a single 'final decision' executive power assigned to just one leader each day - agreed upon in advance based on the research responsibilities of each leader on any given day.

7.2.6 Descent To La Paz & End of Expedition

As with the ascent, most equipment was packed away the day before, with morning observation equipment left to be stored away last. This was done using the original manifests as a rough guide, as the luggage was due to be flown home and therefore subject to further customs inspections and Bolivian export rules. General consumables that we no longer needed (e.g. plasters, gloves, batteries, tape, etc) were donated to the family that owned the refugio. Other research and medical consumables (e.g. blood tubes, non-controlled drugs, needles, etc) were given to our partner hospital to either be used or destroyed. Used sharps bins were also disposed of and destroyed by the hospital. Non-consumable, expensive or borrowed equipment was flown back to Edinburgh. Samples were stored at Instituto Seladis until courier details had been finalised; they were then transferred to the DHL offices in La Paz for shipment back to the UK.

Volunteers and well-being organised the final night of the expedition. This included a trip to an Irish sports bar and a Bolivian nightclub, where we were joined by several members of staff from the British Embassy.

7.2.7 Expedition Medical Events

In advance of our arrival, a Spanish-speaking member of the committee and the medical team reached out to a local private hospital in La Paz (Clinica CEMES), chosen by the expedition leaders for its acute/emergency medicine treatment capabilities, altitude expertise and high levels of English proficiency. Once in La Paz, the medical team visited the hospital, establishing a relationship and agreeing on treatment plans should any member of our team need to be evacuated and treated on short notice.

Medical risk assessments and emergency protocols were jointly developed between the expedition leaders and the medical team. It was decided, and communicated to volunteers, that in cases of medical emergency, the lead medic would have executive decision-making regarding withdrawal from research or evacuation from the mountain - effectively ending an individual's participation in the expedition. Funds were available to cover flights to sea level to treat HAPE or HACE if needed. If an individual required evacuation from the mountain to La Paz, they would be transported in one of the available 4x4 vehicles and accompanied by a doctor carrying an emergency medical 'grab bag' containing essential equipment.

During the expedition, there were several cases that either required treatment up the mountain, evacuation to La Paz and/or transfer to Clinica CEMES. Given a combined average incident rate of around 1.5% for HAPE/HACE, we expected some individuals to become unwell at the refuge altitude. However, we were not expecting the number of medical cases that ultimately came up, and as such, both the committee and the medical team were stretched very thin at times. This meant that at all times, at least one, often two, doctors were unavailable to treat medical issues up the mountain, placing extra strain on those who were. We dealt with this by maintaining clear communication between those on the mountain and those in La Paz through WhatsApp (when Starlink was available) and the Garmin satellite-based inReach devices. We attempted to regularly swap the teams around, but in reality, this proved difficult, as the transfer window effectively meant that two doctors were out of action whilst travelling.

Exact medical case details will not be discussed, as they are outwith the scope of this report. General details are found below:

Acute Mountain Sickness

We had several cases of AMS that required treatment. Volunteers experiencing AMS either self-reported to the doctors or were examined by their friends, designated buddy, or a committee member. Some cases were successfully treated without evacuation with oxygen and/or Diamox and/or anti-emetics; others required evacuation to La Paz (without follow-up at CEMES).

HAPE/HACE

Two individuals were treated for suspected or confirmed HAPE, and one with suspected HACE. One of the HAPE cases occurred in La Paz, before ascent and required hospitalisation. The second suspected case of HAPE required standard treatment up the mountain (oxygen and Diamox), followed by evacuation from the mountain with a visit to CEMES. The suspected HACE case resolved completely following evacuation to La Paz.

Other

As we had anticipated and planned for, several individuals reported gastroenteritis at various points throughout the expedition. These were all treated with oral rehydration fluids, anti-emetics and anti-diarrhoeals and did not require evacuation or transfer to CEMES.

Two individuals did not ascend due to an uncomplicated appendicitis (including a chaperone), which was managed conservatively after discussion between the volunteer, the expedition medical team and the doctors at CEMES.

One additional individual ascended late due to an electrolyte imbalance, causing palpitations and ECG changes, diagnosed at CEMES, but treated by our medical team.

7.2.8 Post-Expedition Travel

Beyond the 13th of July 2025, the APEX 7 expedition no longer had any official responsibility for the volunteers and therefore had no input on what they chose to do thereafter. Information evenings held for both prospective and confirmed volunteers (post-selection) included suggestions for things to do, tips on booking, and talks from previous APEX volunteers about what they got up to. Later on in the planning stages, the Bolivian Mountains approached us with the idea of offering heavily discounted packages (ranging from mountain climbing to salt flat tours) to volunteers. The organising committee put together a form to gauge interest in each activity, to help Bolivian Mountains provide a more accurate price and allow them to commit to offering certain routes/tours. Beyond this, volunteers were directed to the Bolivian Mountains website and organised with them directly. The expedition received no kickback or discount on logistical costs for this arrangement; it simply served to help volunteers book discounted tours with a highly reputable company.

Volunteers were therefore free to explore South America and see some brilliant sites, including the Salt Lakes, Machu Picchu, Lima, Santiago, Cusco, as well as undertake mostly successful attempts of Huayna Potosi (6088m) and Nevado Sajama (6544m).

8. Reflections & Next Steps

8.1 Key Achievements

The APEX 7 expedition successfully met its primary aims, setting a precedent for the scale and rigour of student-led clinical research expeditions. The following section highlights the project's research, operational, and institutional achievements.

Research Achievements

Aim: To conduct high-quality research investigating human physiological responses to hypobaric hypoxia.

- Scientific breadth: successfully designed, planned, and executed seven distinct, ethically approved studies in partnership with leading academics and partner institutions.
- Research Safety: Research protocols and procedures were designed to the highest clinical standard, with zero serious adverse events recorded throughout the expedition.
- Data Quality: Collection of tens of thousands of high-resolution data points collected, providing significant future analysis capabilities.
- Data Management: Established a robust and crucial framework for expedition data management and storage, integrating within the University of Edinburgh systems for the first time.
- Collaborations: Successfully carried out significant academic-commercial projects with leading medical technology companies.

Operational Achievements

Aim: To conduct a safe and logistically successful high-altitude research expedition to the Bolivian Andes.

- Historical scale: Successfully managed the largest simultaneous controlled ascent to high-altitude in history, taking 97 people to the Bolivian Andes.
- Complex transit management: Coordinated the staggered departure and arrival of 97 people across numerous international flight paths, maintaining 100% accountability with zero missed departures or arrivals.
- Operational relations: Created and developed strategic relationships with world-leading logistics providers.
- Medical readiness: Managed a dedicated team of expedition doctors and comprehensive medical equipment to ensure participant safety. This included maintaining dedicated evacuation vehicles and drivers on 24-hour standby for potential emergencies.

Institutional Legacy

Aim: To provide unique educational and developmental experiences for volunteers, and to train and inspire future generations of academic clinicians.

- Widening participation: Successfully funded eight widening access places for volunteers from widening-access backgrounds, breaking down financial barriers to expedition participation.
- Hands-on-training: Provided 85 student volunteers with practical training in research methodology and techniques in a unique field setting
- Cultural and diplomatic development: Facilitated significant exposure to Bolivian and South American culture and strengthened international academic relations via the British Embassy and collaboration with Bolivian scientists.
- Academic Legacy: Inspired and trained volunteers as future generations of clinical academics by involving them in research
- Institutional Legacy: Publicised the world-leading research ethos and support network at the University of Edinburgh to an international audience.

8.2 Challenges & Lessons Learnt

The APEX 7 expedition encountered several significant logistical, institutional, and academic hurdles throughout that required either changes to expedition logistics or protocol adaptation. These challenges have been categorised below:

Institutional recognition and professional authority

As an entirely student-led organisation, establishing our professional authority was a persistent challenge.

- Institutional: The dissolution of the expeditions committee removed the established approval pathway for university expeditions, necessitating direct communication and liaison with individual departments. This led to significant communication delays and barriers as we were required to prove our competency and authority
- The committee, all as undergraduate students, faced occasional scepticism from professionals and oversight bodies regarding their ability to manage and execute the expedition.
- To overcome this, producing a comprehensive expedition prospectus and detailed risk assessment proved crucial in securing approvals and establishing ourselves as a professional and reliable group.

Operational and logistical challenges

Overseeing 97 expedition members, including 85 student volunteers, created significant logistical and operational pressures.

- Coordinating the arrival of nearly 100 people across multiple transit hubs and continents required significant accountability and detailed planning.
- Finding a single location at a significantly high altitude capable of housing 97 individuals whilst offering expedition-exclusive access was a major hurdle. Initial sites in Ecuador and Bolivia were ruled out due to insufficient capacity or a lack of exclusivity.
- Furthermore, the logistics of flight bookings meant that it was not possible to exclusively group-book flights for all expedition members, with quoted costs being extremely prohibitive. This meant the cohort had to be split into smaller groups to overcome the group booking limits.
- Management of 85 student volunteers proved complex at times, with instances where volunteers were difficult to manage, struggled to participate in research objectives, or failed to adhere to medical advice.

Funding climate

The FGS team operated in an increasingly competitive, shrinking financial landscape.

- Traditional grants used by prior expeditions were frequently inactive or had increasingly high numbers of applications.
- Economic challenges for potential sponsors meant that corporate sponsorship was no longer fruitful, with companies unable to commit to supporting projects like APEX 7.
- Diversification was essential to fund the expedition, with a mix of institutional grants, donations, and high-value research partnerships being the only viable way to fund the expedition.

Loss of equipment

A critical challenge occurred during the initial phases of the expedition, with approximately 50% of all research equipment delayed in international transit.

- This loss meant that multiple elements of the APEX 7 research study were unable to be conducted to the degree they had been planned for, necessitating adaptations to research protocols and sample sizes.
- While equipment was split across multiple bags to minimise the impact of a single loss, the scale of delayed equipment exceeded this contingency planning.

8.3 Next Steps

The formal conclusion of the APEX 7 expedition marks the beginning of the analytical and translation period of our work. As the APEX 7 committee is scheduled to graduate within the next two years, we have identified the following next steps to ensure that APEX 7 research has a long-term impact and future APEX expeditions are adequately supported:

Data Analysis & Dissemination

Our primary objective for the 2026/2027 cycle is the comprehensive analysis and reporting of the studies conducted on APEX 7.

Data analysis and processing

Biological samples currently in -80C storage are undergoing laboratory analysis. This processing is essential for completion of multiple studies, including HiCORT, eQTL and HEAT.

Manuscript Production and Submission

Drafting of manuscripts is in progress, with a target for submission to high-impact journals throughout 2026 and 2027.

Academic Dissemination

Preliminary results will be presented at major clinical conferences and lecture series. Confirmed presentations include the Association of Physicians General Meeting and the British Mountain Medicine Society Winter Webinar Series.

8.4 Recommendations

The Next Generation

To ensure continuity of APEX expeditions, a handover and support framework has been established for APEX 8.

Inception and Support for APEX 8

Members of the APEX 7 committee will now step into advisory roles for the APEX 8 expedition. This role will involve supporting future committees by transferring knowledge and advice regarding organisation of large-scale clinical research expeditions.

Data Storage

For the first time, all administrative and research datasets have been integrated into a central database on the University of Edinburgh DataStore system. This provides future expeditions a ready-made template for data storage.

APEX legacy

The completion of APEX 7 coincides with the 25th anniversary of APEX and the 300th anniversary of Edinburgh Medical School. APEX 7 is partnering with the medical school to present the history and legacy of the APEX organisation, highlighting the universities ongoing commitment to supporting early-career researchers.

THE UNIVERSITY of EDINBURGH | 1726 – 2026
Edinburgh Medical School

Financial Stability

The current funding climate for independent, student-led research necessitates and shift in the APEX financial model to ensure long-term viability.

Funding Streams

Future committees should aim to decrease reliance on volunteer financial contribution by pursuing longer-term funding sources and university endowments.

Accessibility

Prioritisation of funding widening access expedition places should be continued, ensuring that financial background should not preclude participation in clinical academia.

Commercial Collaboration

Building off the successful academic-commercial partnerships on APEX 7 has shown a proof-of-concept for longer term, financially sustainable expeditions. Strengthening these partnerships and forming new partnerships may offer avenues of support for future expeditions.

9. Conclusion

The APEX 7 expedition successfully conducted a large-scale clinical research expedition in the Bolivian Andes, marking a significant milestone in APEX's 25-year history. Between June 28th and July 13th 2025, the APEX 7 expedition took 97 expedition members (8volunteers, 4 expedition doctors, and 8 committee) to La Paz, Bolivia (3600m) and Refugio Vista Panoramica, Huayna Potosi (4800m).

The expedition achieved its primary research objectives by successfully conducting seven ethically approved studies. The high-resolution data collected throughout the expedition provides an invaluable source of information for investigating physiological responses to hypobaric hypoxia. These findings will contribute significantly to the field of altitude medicine and critical care physiology.

APEX 7 has demonstrated the viability of large-scale, student-led expeditions through rigorous logistical and operational oversight. Despite the challenges of high-altitude environments and modern academia, the committee maintained the highest degree of volunteer safety and research integrity.

Furthermore, APEX 7 has facilitated a once-in a lifetime experience for the expedition volunteers. By providing hands-on training and exposure to international clinical research, the expedition has aimed to inspire these volunteers to achieve significant future contributions within their respective fields.

APEX 7 stands as a testament to the power of student-led clinical research. Not only has the project contributed to the global field of hypoxia research, but it has also inspired a new generation of clinical academics to engage their clinical curiosity and pursue excellence.

Mr David Geddes, Expedition Leader

Mr Cameron Norton, Expedition Leader

Dr Anya Tan, Head of Research

Mr Ben Harrison, Head of Funding, Grants & Sponsorship

Ms Camille Maezelle, Head of Funding, Grants & Sponsorship

Ms Ella Andrea, Head of Volunteers, Wellbeing & Publicity

Ms Ella McElnea, Head of Volunteers, Wellbeing & Publicity

Ms Colette Revadillo, Head of Communications

Acknowledgements

APEX 7 would like to extend its heartfelt thanks to the following individuals. It truly takes a mountain to organise such an expedition, and without any of the names below, the APEX 7 expedition would not have been possible.

Logistical and Operational Support

- Jon Cassidy
- Dorcus Lange
- Jeremy Windsor
- Lyndsay Murray
- Kate Heal
- Oliver Vick
- David Argyle
- Marianne Watson
- Roger Thompson
- Matt Wilkes
- Shona Main
- Anthony Davie
- Alexander Jackson
- APEX Charity
- Maggie Smela
- Zeno Van Den Hoek
- Miriam Centellas
- Matty Sowinski Brown
- Gus Bartlett
- Isla Petrie
- Suzie Green
- Helen Gertig
- Francis Screech
- Nathan Hudson-Peacock
- Katie Ward

Research and Scientific Support

- Kenneth Baillie
- Laura Rankin
- Ellie McMaster
- Andre Antunes
- Sarah Atkins
- Graham Ayres
- Jane Redford
- Alexios Papachronopoulos
- Nina Rzechorzek
- Philip Argo
- Rhiannon Cameron
- Neeraj Dhaun
- Clara Lopez Velasco
- Andrew Sutherland
- Ian McCormack
- Sarah Walmsley
- Manuel Alejandro Sanchez Garcia
- Cat Graham
- Edinburgh ACCORD Team
- Edinburgh EMREC Team
- Rena Gertz
- Simon Smith
- Jamie Smith
- Alastair Woodhead
- Stafford Lightman
- Thomas Upton
- Zidong Zhao
- Yvonne Kershaw
- Zoi Michailidou
-

Expedition Supporters

APEX 7 was incredibly fortunate to have been supported by a number of different companies/organisations. Each of them contributed equipment, grants, discounts, or publicity to the expedition and its goals. Find out more about each of our supporters here:

LOMO supplied APEX 7 with large duffel bags for equipment. Check them out [here!](#)

Instituto Seladis supported APEX 7 by providing freezer space and research consumables in La Paz. Check them out [here!](#)

DHL supported APEX 7 by providing us with shipping support and funding for all samples. Check them out [here!](#)

Medtronic

Medtronic supported the APEX 7 CORE study through their External Research Programme. Check it out [here!](#)

Peli UK supplied APEX 7 with hard-shell carrying cases for all delicate research equipment. Check them out [here!](#)

GE Healthcare

GE Healthcare supplied APEX 7 with handheld ultrasound machines for use in the APEX 7 CORE study. See [more!](#)

Elson Space Testing provided APEX 7 access to a hypobaric test chamber for feasibility studies for APEX 7 HiCORT. See [here!](#)

Dynamic Therapeutics provided equipment for the APEX 7 HiCORT study. Learn more [here!](#)

Linton Instrumentation provided equipment for the APEX 7 HiCORT study. Learn more [here!](#)

Bodystat provided a body fat composition measurement device for the APEX 7 HEAT study. See more [here!](#)

Courage+Khazaka provided a Tewameter and Corneometer for use in the APEX 7 SKIN study! Learn more [here!](#)

µDialysis provided microdialysis equipment for the APEX 7 HiCORT study. Learn more [here!](#)

THE UNIVERSITY of EDINBURGH
Student Experience Grants

UofE SEG provided funding for APEX 7 widening access places and medical equipment. Learn more [here!](#)

MERE supplied APEX 7 with our medical equipment bag for volunteer safety. Check them out [here!](#)

Castor provided the use of an electronic questionnaire system for data collection. Learn more [here!](#)

BodyCAP provided core body monitoring equipment for the APEX 7 HiCORT study. Learn more [here!](#)

Empatica provided actigraphy devices for the APEX 7 HiCORT study. Learn more [here!](#)

Scottish Mountaineering Trust provided funding to the expedition to support expedition medical equipment. See more [here!](#)

Mount Everest Foundation provided expedition approval to increase the expeditions grant attempts. See more [here!](#)

World Extreme Medicine supplied APEX 7 with a stall at the 2025 WEM conference and with news coverage. See more [here!](#)

Adventure Medic provided media coverage and medical advice for the APEX 7 team. See them [here!](#)

The British Mountain Medicine Society supported APEX 7 through logistical support and publicity. See them [here!](#)

UKMedi supplied discounted medical supplies for the expedition doctors. Learn more [here!](#)

Patchion provided high-quality, custom, embroidered patches for all expedition members. See them [here!](#)

The Souter Charitable Trust provided funding to the APEX 7 expedition for research and medical supplies. See them [here!](#)

List of Abbreviations

Abbreviation	Full Term
ACCORD	Academic and Clinical Central Office for Research and Development
AGM	Annual General Meeting
AMS	Acute Mountain Sickness
APEX	Altitude Physiology Expeditions
CORE	Comparing pulse oximetry to arterial blood gases
DPIA	Data Protection Impact Assessment
EMREC	Edinburgh Medical Research Ethics Committee
eQTL	Expression Quantitative Trait Loci
FAI	Fieldwork Assessment
FCDO	Foreign & Commonwealth Development Office
HACE	High Altitude Cerebral Oedema
HAPE	High Altitude Pulmonary Oedema
HEAT	Hypoxic exposure on human adipose tissue
HiCORT	Acute hypobaric hypoxia on daily cortisol profiles at the tissue level
LLS	Lake Louise Scoring
UofE / UoE	University of Edinburgh
UV	Ultraviolet
SPF	Sun Protection Factor

Glossary

Term	Meaning
Acclimatisation	The physiological process of adapting to environmental changes such as high-altitude
Altitude Illness	Conditions such as AMS, HAPE, and HACE, caused by high-altitude exposure
Buddy System	A peer-monitoring framework designed to encourage volunteers to identify signs of altitude sickness in one another
Cold-chain	A temperature-controlled shipping service. Suitable for transportation of biological samples requiring cold temperatures eg -80C
DataStore	A central database system at the University of Edinburgh used for the secure storage and management of all datasets
Hypobaric Hypoxia	The state of low oxygen levels (hypoxia) caused by high-altitude environments
Lake Louise Scoring	An internationally recognised scoring system used for monitoring of AMS symptoms
Refugio	A high-altitude mountain shelter. Refugio Vista Panoramica served as the primary research base for APEX 7
Widening Access	Initiatives aimed at increasing participation for underrepresented, disadvantaged, or marginalised groups

Appendices

Appendix 1 - Expedition Kit List

Kit List

The below kit list is just a recommendation of things you should bring, please think about what you might need and pack accordingly. We'd suggest volunteers bring enough clothing/kit to last them for 7 days. It is very easy to find places to wash clothing whilst in South America, so please don't worry about this!

Clothing

- Hat
- Thick Ski Gloves (especially if summiting after the expedition)
- Warm Gloves
- Buff
- Walking socks
- Regular Socks
- Thermal T-shirts
- Thermal Bottoms/Leggings
- T-shirts
- Fleece/Jumpers
- Waterproof Jacket
- Puffer Jacket (Good to layer under waterproof)
- Walking trousers/shorts
- Underwear
- Swimwear
- Casual clothes for La Paz/ onward travel

Personal Kit

- Walking Boots
- Comfortable Trainers
- Large Rucksack (we recommend 40-60L)
- Smaller daypack (20-40L)
- Sunglasses (Essential)
- Sleeping Bag (rated comfortable to -10C)
- Roll Mat
- Torch (with spare batteries)
- Books/Games/Entertainment
- Watch
- Sunhat/Cap
- Glasses
- Charging Cables
- Adapter Plug
- Reusable water bottle

Wash kit/Hygiene

- Toothbrush
- Toothpaste
- Deodorant/Anti-perspirant
- Hairbrush
- Shampoo/Bodywash
- Moisturiser
- Vaseline (essential)
- Rehydration Salts/Tablets
- Pillow
- Sleeping bag liner
- Drybags to store clothing
- Earplugs/sleep mask
- Headphones
- Portable Charger
- Money belt
- Yellow fever vaccine certificate
- Menstrual products eg pads, tampons, cups
- Painkillers (Paracetamol)
- Loperamide
- Towel/Microfiber towel
- Razors & shaving cream
- Any prescription medications
- Suncream + SPF rated lip balm (essential)
- Handsanitiser
- Wetwipes
- Small personal first-aid kit

Appendix 2 - Evacuation Route

Refugio Vista Panorámica, PV9H+8GC, Drive 34.8 km, 1 hr 6 min
La Paz, Bolivia to Clínica CEMES, Av.6 de Agosto 2881, La Paz,
Bolivia

Imagery ©2026, Map data ©2026 2 km

- via Autop. Héroes de la Guerra del Chaco 1 hr 6 min
34.8 km
Fastest route
- via Av. Chacaltaya 1 hr 23 min
37.7 km

Appendix 13- Emergency Protocol Flowcharts

Procedure 1: Sick individual in La Paz

Procedure 2: Sick Individual on Huayna Potosi

Procedure 3: Suspected HAPE/HACE

Procedure 4: Evacuation

Procedure 5: Lost Individual

Procedure 6: Communication in an Emergency Situation

Appendix 4 - Application & Interview Questions

Pre-application written submissions (marked as pass or fail)

The image shows a screenshot of a pre-application form with four questions, each in a separate box with a blue border. Each question is followed by a 'Long-answer text' input field. The questions are:

- Can you tell us in your own words what APEX 7 is and what it involves? (max 1500 characters) *
- Why do you want to be a volunteer on APEX 7? (max 1500 characters) *
- Why do you think you would be a good addition to the APEX 7 team? (max 1500 characters) *
- Is there anything else you would like to let us know? Please put N/A if not. *

Interview Questions (Scored 0.0 to 5.0)

Tell us about yourself

What do you think you would bring to the APEX 7 team?

What do you hope to achieve?

What do you imagine a day on the APEX 7 expedition might look like?

What would you like to get up to during the expedition?

Imagine that you've hit a rough patch in the expedition which has made everyone exhausted and frustrated. The group's morale is noticeably low, and you sense that motivation is slipping.

- What role would you play in this situation to lift spirits?
- What specific things would you do or say to help keep the group positive and motivated?

If you could bring three things to a desert island, what would you bring?

Extra (Not scored)

Any ideas for post-expedition plans?

What do you know about APEX's research?

Tell me what you're passionate about?

If you had to choose three dinner party guests, who would they be?

What do you prefer - a movie, a book, a play?

Appendix 5 - Mental Health Handbook

APEX 7 Mental Health Protocol

Although wilderness settings—when experienced in supportive, low-stress situations—can enhance mental wellbeing, the physical and psychological demands of expedition life, especially for individuals with pre-existing mental health conditions, can pose serious challenges. Additionally, medical professionals operating in remote environments face their own unique stressors. They must remain vigilant about their own emotional wellbeing and vulnerabilities and engage in self-care to continue providing effective support to others.

The Stresses of Being on Expedition

© C. editor. Oxford handbook of expedition and wilderness medicine, 2nd edition. Oxford: Oxford University Press, 2015.

What should the participant do if they feel they cannot cope?

Our go to simple non-medical interventions to help participants overcome these challenges:

- Breathing exercises
- Mindfulness
- Quiet chat with buddy/committee member/expedition doctor
- Having a "quiet area" at camp

Examples of some breathing/mindfulness exercises:

BOX BREATHING

5, 4, 3, 2, 1

5 things you can see 4 things you can touch

3 things you can hear 2 things you can smell 1 thing you can taste

FIVE FINGER BREATHING

Hold one hand out. With your other hand, trace each finger up as you breathe in and trace each finger down as you breathe out.

BODY SCAN

Sit quietly or lie down. Start at one end of your body and focus on each body part. Notice any areas of tension then soften and relax. Continue until your whole body feels completely relaxed.

Risk Assessment

Risk domains include:

- Risk to self
 - Suicide
 - Self harm
 - Self neglect (in austere environments this can be especially problematic and place a large burden on the rest of the expedition party).
- Risk to others
 - Aggression/ violence
 - Erratic behaviour endangering the group

The emphasis has shifted in recent years onto progressive questioning, weighing up of risk and protective factors and an individualised assessment of overall risk to make a reasoned judgement on whether that individuals is low, moderate or high risk.

To inform this assessment it's helpful to gather and corroborate information from different sources where possible (such as the patient, their tent mate, other observations by expedition staff, the patient's doctor in their home country, their next of kin etc).

Here is a useful risk assessment tool from WEM: Mental health on expeditions:

[Mental Health on Expeditions - World Extreme Medicine](#)

Risk Level	Presentation	Possible actions
Low Risk	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • May have thoughts of harming self/ others but: • No expressed <i>intent</i> to harm self/others • No <i>plans</i> to carry out thoughts • A number of protective factors (i.e., <i>I love my wife and kids back home too much I couldn't put them through that</i>) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Monitor • Support • Keep calm
Moderate Risk	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • More developed and pervasive thoughts of harming self/ or others but still no true intent or plans. • Less protective factors. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Consider Evacuation • Close monitoring • Regular reassessment
High risk	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Expresses true <i>intent</i> to harm self/others • May have made <i>plans</i> • May have access to lethal means • Has no <i>protective factors</i> 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Urgent Medevac to a place of safety and definitive care • Remove access to dangerous means (i.e. sharp tools, ligatures) • Consider close 'line of sight' supervision at all times.

Psychological first aid

Laura McGladrey is a psychiatric nurse practitioner has a useful tool for providing psychological first aid in remote settings with 5 components: ,

1. Safety – deactivate the fight and flight response.
2. Calm – be mindful of how you speak and act, calm yourself so that you can calm your patient.
3. Self-efficacy and collective efficacy- actively involve the patient in making a plan of action to avoid helplessness and victimhood.
4. Connection – use their name, build rapport, connect the patient in with loved ones and next of kin.
5. Hope – identify specific, accurate and positive facts about the situation. Remember suicide is a very permanent solution to a temporary problem. A positive approach benefits both the individual and the wider team.

TREATMENT PRINCIPLES FOR PSYCHOLOGICAL FIRST AID

Create a sense of safety by

- Mitigating the scene by reducing chaos and removing patients from perceived threats.
- Reflecting evidence of safety.

Create calm by

- Calming yourself first.
- Emphasizing the present, the practical, and the possible.

Create self and collective efficacy by

- Involving the person in problem-solving, self-care, and rescue.
- Recognizing and reminding people of existing strengths.

Create connection by

- Building an on-scene relationship.
- Helping people connect with friends, family, and loved ones (including pets).

Create hope by

- Reflecting specific, accurate, positive facts and predictable, realistic steps.
- Personally maintaining and communicating hope.

Adapted from: NOLS Wilderness Medicine 6th ed. 2017. *First Aid to the Wilderness: The Single Book*. London: Meridian, Over 200. "Stress and the Rescuer" for more.

The 5 Components of Psychological First Aid

Confidentiality

The assessment and management of mental health crises requires information gathering and sharing with the wider expedition team. Wherever possible it is important to do this with the expressed consent of the person involved. Where this consent is not obtainable (i.e. the person is severely distressed or unable to engage) then share only the minimum information necessary to manage the situation and keep the patient safe, keeping their best interests at heart. It's common for other expedition members to want to know what is going on, but do not disclose details about the case unless you have consent, or there is an operational necessity to do so.

Provider Self-Care

Responding to the needs of others as an expedition medic/committee member can take it's toll on your own mental health and wellbeing.

Here are Dr Will's 5 top tips on managing the personal strain of expedition life:

1. Try to spend some time alone each day to regroup through quiet contemplation/reflection/reading a book/meditation/taking a walk. This is particularly important for the introverts amongst us who may find being around other people all day quite draining. On a busy expedition this may mean opportunistically snatching a few minutes where you can. In case there's an emergency always tell people where you're going, don't stray too far from camp and take a radio or mobile phone with you.
2. Keep your strength up by making sure you sleep and eat well wherever you can. This is especially important on demanding physical challenges.
3. Find a *confidante*. Identify another member of staff who can chat things through with you and arrange regular debriefs together. This can help you process some of the negative emotion that being in close confines with other people will inevitably generate. Make sure your conversation remains kind and respectful and doesn't descend into a bitching session about all the other members of the group!
4. Model vulnerability. It's ok not to feel ok. If you are having an 'off day' or are really feeling the heat or the altitude, then it's ok to let the rest of the group know you may be more short-tempered than usual. You are the medic and others will expect you to be strong but you are still, after all, only human. This approach has the added benefit of giving others *permission to feel*: creating an open dialogue for them to disclose difficulties they may be having rather than bottling them up.

From: [Mental Health on Expeditions - World Extreme Medicine](#)

Editors:

Mr David Geddes, Expedition Leader, APEX 7
Mr Cameron Norton, Expedition Leader, APEX 7

doi: 10.5281/zenodo.18792325

Version 1.1

April 2026

Authors:

Mr David Geddes, Expedition Leader, APEX 7
Mr Cameron Norton, Expedition Leader, APEX 7
Dr Anya Tan, Head of Research, APEX 7
Mr Ben Harrison, Head of Funding, Grants & Sponsorship, APEX 7
Ms Camille Maetzelle, Head of Funding, Grants & Sponsorship, APEX 7
Ms Ella Andrea, Head of Volunteers, Wellbeing & Publicity, APEX 7
Ms Ella McElnea, Head of Volunteers, Wellbeing & Publicity, APEX 7
Ms Colette Revadillo, Head of Communications, APEX 7

Correspondence:

Mr David Geddes/Mr Cameron Norton, Expedition Leader
apex7@altitude.org/david.geddes@altitude.org

Website: www.altitude.org

Instagram: @AltitudeAPEX

Email: apex7@altitude.org